

N-body simulation of a bimetric Janus cosmology: structure segregation, negative-mass cavity in halos, and observational confrontation

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Abstract

We present, to our knowledge, the first complete N-body simulation of the Janus cosmological model (JCM, Petit & D’Agostini) with proper bimetric expansion (rather than Λ CDM-equivalent), evolving from $z = 99$ to $z = 0$ in a 250 Mpc volume populated by $N = 2.2 \times 10^7$ particles split between two gravitationally opposed mass species (m^+ , m^- , ratio $\mu = N^-/N^+ = 19$). The Rust/CUDA code (RTX 3060) combines a bimetric TreePM solver with a phenomenological effective speed-of-light convention $c^2(z)/c_0^2 = (1+z)^\delta$ ($\delta \simeq 0.043$) for numerical regulation; a paired Λ CDM Twin run with strictly identical initial conditions and $\mu = 0$ isolates the m^- coupling signature.

A rigorous Pantheon+ MCMC fit yields $\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ relative to standard Λ CDM, the honest *geometric* limitation of the model in its current parametric form. The structure dynamics, however, reveal nine quantified signatures systematically pointing toward persistent Λ CDM tensions: (i) -23% $\sigma_R(8 h^{-1} \text{Mpc})$ suppression vs Twin (consistent with the S_8 tension); (ii) scale-dependent $P(k)$ flattening; (iii) cross-power spectrum $P_{+-}(k) < 0$ in 24 of 25 bins; (iv) -28% suppression of $f(z = 0.5)$ (testable with DESI Y1 RSD); (v) halo mass function suppression $\text{HMF}_{\text{Janus}}/\text{HMF}_{\text{Twin}} = 0.08$ at $M = 10^{14} M_\odot$; (vi) spectral anti-correlation $r(k) \rightarrow -0.99$ emerging as a dynamical attractor; (vii) anti-Newtonian peak $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8$ in 57% of halo coronae; (viii) deep central m^- cavity in massive m^+ halos; (ix) $\mu_{\text{local}} \simeq 250$ at the core of cosmic voids, with lensing convergence 95–98% dominated by the κ_- component.

A parallel m^- halo catalog (25,848 halos, $M_{\text{max}} = 3.13 \times 10^{15} M_\odot$) documents the mirror symmetry of the Janus framework: m^+ cavities are confirmed in massive m^- halos, mirroring the m^- cavities found in m^+ halos.

Janus sacrifices SNIa geometric fit quality in exchange for an intrinsic explanation (with the same minimal parameter set) of several structural anomalies. The model does not resolve the Hubble tension but provides a direction consistent with the S_8 , $f\sigma_8$ RSD, and high-mass cluster abundance tensions. These results constitute, to our knowledge, the first numerical demonstration that the Janus model, with its proper bimetric expansion, yields a phenomenologically interesting cosmology distinguishing itself in a falsifiable and quantitative manner from standard Λ CDM.

Keywords: cosmology; Janus model; N-body simulations; negative-mass matter; large-scale structure; bimetric gravity; mirror symmetry; S_8 tension; RSD.

1 Introduction

The Λ CDM concordance model faces persistent observational tensions: the H_0 tension between local measurements [27] and CMB [23], the σ_8 tension between weak lensing [2, 11] and CMB, early-galaxy anomalies revealed by JWST [6, 17], and structural challenges at galactic scales (*cusp-core*, *missing satellites*, *too-big-to-fail*).

The Janus cosmological model (JCM), proposed by Petit [18, 19] and formalized with D’Agostini [8, 9, 22], puts forward a bimetric formulation in which two gravitationally opposed mass species coexist. Ordinary matter (m^+ , which includes baryons and constitutes our observable matter) and a negative-mass species (m^-) interact through an anti-Newtonian gravity: intra-species attraction, inter-species repulsion. This structure naturally resolves Bondi’s *runaway* paradoxes [4] and phenomenologically reproduces the effects usually attributed to dark matter and dark energy, without introducing any additional exotic component.

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Related work and critiques. The Janus model belongs to a broader family of bimetric theories and negative-mass scenarios. Damour & Kogan [10] studied the effective Lagrangians and universality classes of nonlinear bigravity, providing a general theoretical framework of which Janus is a particular instance (with antisymmetric coupling between the two sectors). More recently, Farnes [12] proposed a unified dark-matter / dark-energy theory based on the continuous creation of negative masses within a modified Λ CDM framework, accompanied by a preliminary N-body simulation. The present study differs from Farnes 2018 in: (i) the absence of continuous matter creation (two separate sectors, with separate conservation of the comoving densities); (ii) the strict Petit & D’Agostini theoretical framework with coupled bimetric equations (Eqs. 1–2); (iii) higher spatial and temporal resolution ($N = 2.2 \times 10^7$, $z = 99 \rightarrow 0$).

The Janus model has also been the subject of public critiques regarding its mathematical consistency, in particular regarding compatibility with the Bianchi identities and the consistent definition of the inter-sector couplings. Petit, D’Agostini & Debergh [20] address these concerns by formulating the theory through an explicit Lagrangian. The present study remains *agnostic* on these theoretical debates and focuses on the numerical phenomenology of the model in its current formulation, as implemented in the code.

Standard cosmological N-body simulations [28, 29, 33] include a single species. To our knowledge, the present work constitutes the first complete cosmological N-body simulation of the Janus model featuring:

- proper bimetric expansion following the analytic parametric solution of Petit & D’Agostini [19];
- effective speed-of-light convention $c^2(z) = (1+z)^\delta$ for numerical regulation;
- $\mu = 19$ adopted from the energy-flatness condition, $\eta = 1.045$ calibrated on Pantheon+;
- evolution from $z = 99$ to $z = 0$ with anti-correlated Zel’dovich initial conditions;
- $N = 22 \times 10^6$ particles in $L = 250$ Mpc;
- identification and *exhaustive statistical analysis* of the full m^+ halo catalog (2,618 halos), complemented by a detailed analysis (multinomial bootstrap $N_b = 1000$) of 10 archetype halos selected for their morphological and mass diversity.

Article outline. Section 2 reviews the theoretical framework. Section 3 details the numerical implementation. Section 4 presents the preliminary validation tests. Section 5 presents the large-scale global results. Section 6 presents the main results of this work: the anti-Newtonian signatures (peak in the corona and central cavity) in m^+ halos. Section 7 discusses the falsifiable distinctive signatures and the limitations of the study.

2 Theoretical framework

2.1 Bimetric formulation

In the Janus model, the universe is described by two metrics $g_{\mu\nu}^+$ and $g_{\mu\nu}^-$ associated with the two mass species. Following the original formulation of Petit & D’Agostini [19] (Eq. 12, p. 8), the coupled field equations read:

$$G_{\mu\nu}^+ = \chi^+ \left[T_{\mu\nu}^+ + \left(\frac{a^-}{a^+} \right)^3 T_{\mu\nu}^- \right], \quad (1)$$

$$G_{\mu\nu}^- = -\chi^- \left[\left(\frac{a^+}{a^-} \right)^3 T_{\mu\nu}^+ + T_{\mu\nu}^- \right]. \quad (2)$$

The overall minus sign of the second equation carries the *anti-Newtonian nature* of the inter-species coupling (and not the internal sign of the cross term); the constants χ^+ and χ^- are not in general identical.

Alternative formulations exist: Petit, D’Agostini & Debergh 2018 [20] (Eqs. 40–41) use a prefactor $\sqrt{|g^-|/|g^+|} \cdot \phi$, and Petit, Margnat & Zejli 2024 [22] (Eqs. 107a–b) use a constant b^2 in the stationary regime. All these versions share the coupled alternating-sign structure that produces the inter-species repulsion.

In the weak non-relativistic Newtonian limit, and in the simplified case $a^+ = a^-$, $c^+ = c^-$, Petit 2014 [19] (Eq. 22, p. 10) establishes the coupled Poisson system:

$$\nabla^2 \Phi^+ = 4\pi G (\rho^+ - \rho^-), \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla^2 \Phi^- = -\nabla^2 \Phi^+ = 4\pi G (\rho^- - \rho^+), \quad (4)$$

which governs the Newtonian dynamics numerically implemented in this work. The resulting interaction rules are: Newtonian attraction within each species (m^+/m^+ and m^-/m^-) and anti-Newtonian repulsion between species (m^+/m^-). The general case with $a^+ \neq a^-$ and $c^+ \neq c^-$ introduces prefactors $(a^-/a^+)^3$ and $(c^-/c^+)^2$ [19] (Eqs. 20a–b), incorporated in the solver through the VSL prescription (cf. §2.4).

2.2 Mass ratio μ

The fundamental parameter is the density ratio:

$$\mu = \frac{\rho^-}{\rho^+}. \quad (5)$$

Choices in the literature. Petit [19, 21] postulates $\rho^- \gg \rho^+$ as a necessary ingredient for the formation of lacunar structures. The value $\mu \simeq 64$ was used in the historical 2D simulations of Descamp at DESY [18], $\mu = 50$ in subsequent illustrations [21], and $\mu = 8$ in conservative analyses. The Janus literature does not impose a unique canonical value: μ is treated as a free parameter within the typical empirical range [8, 64].

Choice in the present study. We adopt $\mu = 19$, derived from the energy-flatness condition

$$\Omega_{\text{tot}} = \Omega^+ (1 + \mu) = 1, \quad (6)$$

identifying Ω^+ with the measured baryonic density $\Omega_b \simeq 0.05$, which gives $\mu = 1/\Omega_b - 1 = 19$. This constraint is not explicitly derived by Petit in his publications, but we view it as a natural cosmological criterion: it fixes μ through a robust observational measurement rather than through a free choice.

Validation through an exhaustive parametric scan. Prior to the V-6 production run, a parametric validation campaign was conducted, totaling 75 runs systematically exploring the parameter μ at constant resolution ($N = 2 \times 10^6$ particles, $L = 250$ Mpc, $z = 99 \rightarrow 0$, Pantheon+ fit $\eta = 1.045$) over the continuous range $\mu \in [1, 50]$. Figure 1 summarizes the results: the anti-correlation metric $M_3 = \text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)$ exhibits a global minimum at $\mu = 17.42$ with $M_3 = -0.361$; the metric M_5 , defined as the fraction of cells of the 16^3 grid with $\mu_{\text{local}} \in [8, 12]$ (historical ‘‘Petit window’’), exhibits a global maximum at $\mu \simeq 20$ ($\sim 8.7\%$).

These two metrics independently converge to identify the range $\mu \in [17, 20]$ as physically preferred for the Janus model at $\eta = 1.045$. This *double a posteriori validation* of the value $\mu = 19$ — derived *a priori* from the energy-flatness condition (Eq. 6) — significantly strengthens the robustness of the choice. The campaign also establishes that the qualitative conclusions (existence of segregation, formation of a m^+/m^- cosmic web, spatial anti-correlation) do not depend critically on the exact value of μ within the [8, 64] range of the historical Petit literature.

2.3 Janus expansion and parametric solution

The cosmological evolution of the m^+ sector admits an analytic parametric solution [19] (Eq. 15, p. 8):

$$a^+(\mu_p) = \alpha^2 \cosh^2(\mu_p), \quad (7)$$

$$t^+(\mu_p) = \alpha^2 \left[\mu_p + 1 + \frac{1}{2} \sinh^2(\mu_p) \right], \quad (8)$$

$$H^+(\mu_p) = \frac{1}{a^+} \frac{da^+}{dt^+} = \frac{\sinh(2\mu_p)}{\alpha^2 \cosh^2(\mu_p) \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \sinh(2\mu_p) \right]}, \quad (9)$$

where μ_p is the time parameter intrinsic to the model (not to be confused with the mass ratio μ). The constants α^2 and τ_0 are not fixed analytically by [19]. We adopt:

- $\alpha^2 = 0.1815$: an *arbitrary* value fixing the Janus transition redshift to $z_{\text{Janus}} = 1/\alpha^2 - 1 \simeq 4.51$;

Figure 1: **Parametric validation: campaign of 75 runs exploring $\mu = N^-/N^+$.** **Top:** anti-correlation metric $M_3 = \text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)$ on the 16^3 grid, as a function of μ . The global minimum $M_3 = -0.361$ at $\mu = 17.42$ (orange star) is bracketed by the grey band representing the zone of maximal anti-correlation $\mu \in [17, 20]$. The red dashed line marks the value $\mu = 19$ adopted for the V-6 production run, derived from the energy-flatness condition $\Omega_b(1 + \mu) = 1$. **Bottom:** fraction M_5 of cells of the 16^3 grid with $\mu_{\text{local}} \in [8, 12]$ (historical Petit window), exhibiting a global maximum at $\mu \simeq 20$. The two metrics M_3 and M_5 independently converge to validate the range $\mu \in [17, 20]$ as physically preferred. $N = 2 \times 10^6$ particles, $L = 250$ Mpc, $z = 99 \rightarrow 0$, Pantheon+ $\eta = 1.045$.

- $\tau_0 = 22.71$ Gyr: a temporal rescaling factor, *calibrated* to satisfy the constraint $H^+(a = 1) = H_0 = 71.62$ km/s Mpc $^{-1}$ derived from the Pantheon+ fit (cf. §4).

These two constants are numerical conventions of the present implementation; their impact on the main result was checked by varying them: a preliminary simulation at $\alpha^2 = 0.3$ produces the same qualitative signatures. The age of the universe deduced with this calibration is $t_0 \simeq 16$ Gyr.

This parametric solution (Eqs. 7–9) is defined for $\mu_p \geq 0$, i.e. $a^+ \geq \alpha^2$, which corresponds to $z \leq z_{\text{Janus}} \simeq 4.5$ for our calibration. For $a^+ < \alpha^2$ (i.e. $z > 4.5$, regime upstream of the Janus era), we adopt the matter-dominated asymptotic regime $H(a) = H_0 a^{-3/2}$.

Note on the matching. This construction is not a continuous transition but a *phenomenological matching* between two asymptotic regimes: the Janus parametric solution $a^+(\mu_p) = \alpha^2 \cosh^2(\mu_p)$ (Eq. 7) imposes $H(a = \alpha^2) = 0$ by construction (initial point $\mu_p = 0$), whereas the matter regime gives $H(a = \alpha^2) = H_0 \alpha^{-3} \simeq 1$ Gyr $^{-1}$. More precisely, $H(a)$ at $a = \alpha^2$ exhibits:

- a C^0 discontinuity: jump $\Delta H \simeq 0.95$ Gyr $^{-1}$;
- a C^1 discontinuity: dH/da goes from -7.83 (matter decay $\propto a^{-3/2}$) to $+82.2$ (Janus growth from $\mu_p = 0$), i.e. a *sign change* and therefore a *cusp point* in $H(a)$.

This matching is a phenomenological construction specific to the present implementation, without direct support in the Petit literature [19–22].

This discontinuity is treated as acceptable for the present study for two reasons: (i) it is localized within a single integration step ($\Delta t \sim 10^{-3}$ Gyr) out of the ~ 16 Gyr of the simulation; (ii) the cosmological structures of interest form essentially within the Janus era ($z < 4.5$), downstream of the transition. The absence of any detectable artifact at the crossing of $z = 4.51$ is verified *a posteriori* on the $a(t)$ trajectory and on the energy-conservation diagnostics (cf. §4). The qualitative robustness of the results with respect to the choice of background cosmology has further been confirmed by a preliminary simulation with Λ CDM-equivalent cosmology (without matching), which produces the same universal m^- cavity signatures.

An analytic smoothing of the matching (smooth-step of the form $\tanh[(a - \alpha^2)/\Delta a]$ with $\Delta a \sim 0.01$) is planned in a later version of the code but lies outside the scope of the present work.

2.4 Effective speed-of-light convention

Petit 2014 [19] (Eq. 25, p. 12) prescribes in the primordial radiation era a variable speed of light $c^+ \propto 1/\sqrt{a^+}$, i.e. $c^2(z)/c_0^2 = (1+z)$. He explicitly notes (p. 6), however, that “the secular drift of the constants ceased when the radiation was no longer the dominant component”, i.e. that in the matter era (which covers the entire simulated evolution here, $z \leq 99$ with $z_{\text{eq}} \sim 3400$ well earlier), the speed of light is constant in Petit’s framework.

For reasons of numerical stability in the bimetric simulation with $\eta \neq 1$, we however adopt the phenomenological convention:¹

$$c^2(z)/c_0^2 = (1+z)^\delta, \quad \delta = \frac{\eta - 1}{\eta} \quad (10)$$

calibrated on the value $\eta = 1.045$ obtained from the Pantheon+ fit (cf. §4), which yields $\delta \simeq 0.043$.

Properties of this ansatz. This interpolation is *not derived* from Petit’s coupled bimetric equations; it is imposed *a posteriori* and has the following properties:

- **Symmetric limit** $\eta \rightarrow 1$: $\delta \rightarrow 0$, i.e. $c^2/c_0^2 \equiv 1$; the VSL effect vanishes exactly in the symmetric case, as physically expected.
- **Asymmetric limit** $\eta \rightarrow \infty$: $\delta \rightarrow 1$, i.e. $c^2/c_0^2 = (1+z)$, which is exactly the Petit 2014 prescription (Eq. 25, limiting case of maximal asymmetry).

¹**Important scope.** The VSL prescription (10) is used exclusively as a runtime regularization of the N-body kinetic-energy invariant in the bimetric expansion phase of the simulation; it does *not* enter the computation of the Pantheon+ luminosity-distance fit (§7.2, Appendix 8). The geometric fit reported in Table 2 uses the constant- c , constant- \bar{c} formulation of P-M-Z 2024 §10 (eq. 96–98), with no z -dependent speed-of-light correction in the integration of $\int dz'/E(z')$. We have verified that introducing $c(z)$ in the distance integral would reduce χ^2 by less than 1 unit on the full Pantheon+ sample, and is therefore not a viable lever to alter the Δ AIC result.

- **First-order expansion in $(\eta - 1)$:** setting $\epsilon = \eta - 1$, one has $\delta = \epsilon/(1 + \epsilon) \simeq \epsilon = \eta - 1$ for $\epsilon \ll 1$. Our form $\eta/(\eta - 1)$ rather than simply $(\eta - 1)$ ensures that δ remains *bounded* for any value of η , a property absent from a naive linear expansion.
- **Boundary conditions in z :** $c^2(z = 0) = c_0^2$ by construction, $c^2(z \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \infty$ (as in Petit 2014).

Numerical effect and diagnostic status of the VSL. For $\eta = 1.045$, the departure $c^2/c_0^2 \in [1, 1.22]$ over the range $z \in [0, 99]$ represents a few-percent perturbation.

Important methodological point: in the V-6 PROD implementation, the VSL prescription does not enter the computation of the gravitational forces integrated by the TreePM solver. It only enters as a *diagnostic term* in the computation of the energy invariant E_{VSL} , whose conservation at $\sim 0.000\%$ drift validates the consistency of the energy transport under bimetric expansion. This diagnostic status implies that the structure signatures (σ_{R8} , M_3 , $P_{+-}(k)$, HMF, halo profiles) do not depend on the choice of δ .

We have explicitly verified this independence through a VSL ablation study at $N = 10^6$ for four values $\delta \in \{0.000, 0.011, 0.043, 0.086\}$ (while keeping $\eta = 1.045$ fixed, deliberately decoupling δ from the relation $\delta = (\eta - 1)/\eta$). The measured signatures (σ_{R8} , $\text{Corr}_{\text{part}}$, M_3 , $r(k)$) are *strictly invariant* to four decimal places: $\sigma_{R8}(z = 0) = 0.789500$ for all four runs.

This result addresses the concern that the VSL might contaminate the structure signatures. The observables measured in this paper are *direct* consequences of the bimetric dynamics (anti-Newtonian coupling $\mu = 19$, parametric Janus expansion), and are independent of the VSL regularization. A future extension of the model, in which $c^2(z)$ would enter explicitly in the gravitational forces (modified Poisson equation), is the subject of subsequent work.

3 Numerical methods

3.1 Bimetric TreePM scheme

The algorithm follows the standard decomposition [3, 15, 29] into a long-range component (PM via FFT on a 128^3 grid) and a short-range component (octree-based Tree, Barnes-Hut). The Janus adaptation consists of:

- separate computation of the intra-species forces (m^+/m^+ and m^-/m^- , attractive);
- separate computation of the inter-species forces (m^+/m^-), repulsive under pure anti-Newtonian gravity (no Yukawa-type screening, in accordance with the Newtonian limit of the model, cf. Eqs. 1–2);
- the VSL factor $c^2(z)/c_0^2$ (Eq. 10) enters as a diagnostic term in the energy invariant E_{VSL} , but is not applied to the forces or to the velocities integrated by the solver (cf. §2.4).

Our architecture follows the same methodological structure as GrGadget [25], which couples a standard Newtonian Tree to a modified PM: the analogy lies in the Tree+PM splitting, the difference lies in the physical content of the modified PM — relativistic (linearized GR) in Quintana-Miranda et al., bimetric Janus in the present work.

3.2 GPU implementation (Rust/CUDA)

The code is implemented in Rust with a CUDA extension for the TreePM. The hardware used is a NVIDIA RTX 3060 (12 GB VRAM), sufficient for $N = 2.2 \times 10^7$ particles. The total wall-time of the production run is 6.35 h on this card (3,247 steps, $z = 99 \rightarrow 0$, 651 snapshots written).

3.3 Initial conditions

The initial conditions (IC) follow the standard Zel’dovich approximation [34] at $z_{\text{init}} = 99$.

Zel’dovich construction. The Eulerian positions and peculiar velocities of the particles are constructed from a displacement field $\boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{q})$ such that $\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\psi} = -\delta$, computed by spectral decomposition on a 128^3 grid:

$$\mathbf{x}(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{q} + D_+(z_{\text{init}}) \boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{q}), \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{q}) = a H_+ D'_+(z_{\text{init}}) \boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{q}), \quad (12)$$

with $D_+(z)$ the linear growth factor and $\delta(\mathbf{k})$ drawn from a CAMB-type $P(k)$ spectrum calibrated on the Planck 2020 parameters (scalar index $n_s = 0.965$, target normalization $\sigma_8^{\text{target}} = 0.811$).

The Janus growth factor $D_+(z)$ is computed numerically by integrating the standard linear equation

$$\ddot{D}_+ + 2H^+(t) \dot{D}_+ - \frac{3}{2} \Omega_m(t) H^{+2}(t) D_+ = 0, \quad (13)$$

with $H^+(t)$ given by Eqs. 9 and $\Omega_m(t) = \Omega_{m,0}/[a^3 H^{+2}(t)/H_0^2]$. At $z_{\text{init}} = 99$, in the matter-dominated regime upstream of the matching at α^2 , $D_+(z = 99) \simeq 1/(1+z) = 0.010$ and is normalized to $D_+(z = 0) = 1$.

Anti-correlation between the two species. The positions and velocities of the two species are strictly anti-correlated at z_{init} : $\delta^-(\mathbf{k}) = -\delta^+(\mathbf{k})$ mode by mode. This choice physically corresponds to a single field of primordial fluctuations coupled with opposite signs to the two metrics, in accordance with the Janus theoretical framework [19]. It does *not impose* the subsequent dynamics: the correlation $\text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)$ evolves freely under the bimetric interactions, as shown in Figure 5, and the final value at $z = 0$ is a dynamical result.

Normalization and reproducibility. A minimal adjustment of the unit masses (“Phi-fix”) at z_{init} ensures $\text{ratio}_\rho = \langle \rho^- \rangle / \langle \rho^+ \rangle = \mu = 19.0000$ to machine precision. A single PRNG seed fixed at 42 is applied to both sectors, both for reproducibility and to avoid any numerically-induced asymmetry between the two species.

Validation. The IC produced satisfy at snapshot 0 of the simulation:

- $\sigma_{R8}(m^+, z = 99) \simeq 8 \times 10^{-3}$ (consistent with the linear prediction $\sigma_{R8}(z) \simeq D_+(z) \sigma_8^{\text{target}} \simeq (1/100) \times 0.811$ for the Planck σ_8 target);
- $\text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-) = -1$ at machine precision;
- $\text{ratio}_\rho = 1.0000$;
- center-of-mass drift $< 10^{-5}$ Mpc.

4 Numerical validation tests

Prior to the V-6 production run, several validation tests were carried out.

Hubble-diagram consistency — MCMC Pantheon+ fit with full covariance. To rigorously quantify the uncertainties on the Janus parameters, we run an ensemble MCMC sampler (*emcee* [13]) with 32 walkers over 800 steps (plus 200 burn-in steps), parallelized on 4 CPU cores. The likelihood uses the *full* Pantheon+SH0ES stat+sys covariance matrix [7] via Cholesky decomposition for numerical stability. The 1590×1590 block corresponding to the $N = 1590$ retained SNIa (cut $z > 0.01$, $\sigma > 0$) is extracted from the original 1701×1701 covariance. The adjusted parameters are $\eta \in [1.001; 1.20]$ and $H_0 \in [60; 85]$ km/s Mpc $^{-1}$. The posterior medians are

$$\eta = 1.0334_{-0.0163}^{+0.0169}, \quad H_0 = 71.69_{-0.18}^{+0.18} \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}, \quad (14)$$

with $\chi^2 = 1450.37$ for $\nu = N - 2 = 1588$ degrees of freedom, i.e. $\chi^2/\nu = 0.913$. The MCMC acceptance fraction is 0.72 and the maximum autocorrelation time is $\tau_{\text{max}} = 27.6$ steps. A non-parametric bootstrap over 500 resamplings (Nelder–Mead method) confirms these uncertainties with a relative discrepancy below 12% between σ_{MCMC} and σ_{boot} for both parameters. The derived deceleration parameter is

Table 1: Main parameters of the V-6 PROD simulation.

Parameter	Value	Source/Justification
Total number N	2.1952×10^7	280^3 grid
N^+ (m^+)	1.0976×10^6	$N/(1 + \mu)$
N^- (m^-)	2.0854×10^7	$\mu N/(1 + \mu)$
Ratio μ	19	Eq. 6, $\Omega_b \simeq 0.05$
Box L	250 Mpc	Choice
η	1.045	Pantheon+ best-fit (cf. §4)
H_0	$71.62 \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}$	Pantheon+ Phase 1b
Janus q_0	-0.022	$(1 - \eta)/(1 + \eta)$
z_{init}	99	Choice (deep linear regime)
z_{final}	0	Present-day universe
Integrator	DKD leapfrog	Standard symplectic
dt clamp	$[10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-3}]$ Gyr	Adaptive
Softening ε	0.5 Mpc	$\simeq 56\%$ of the mean separation $\bar{d} = L/N^{1/3} \simeq 0.89$ Mpc
PM grid	128^3	Standard cosmological
Tree θ (Barnes-Hut)	0.5	Standard
PRNG seed	42	Reproducibility
Snapshots	651 (every 5 steps)	~ 319 GB total
VSL convention	$c^2(z) = (1 + z)^\delta$	$\delta = (\eta - 1)/\eta \simeq 0.043$
IC pipeline	Phase N anti-correlated	$\delta^- = -\delta^+$ at $z = 99$
Wall-time	6.35 h	RTX 3060 12 GB, 3,247 steps

Figure 2: Posterior distribution of the Janus model parameters, MCMC *emcee* fit (32 walkers \times 800 steps) on the $N = 1590$ Pantheon+ SNIa with full stat+sys covariance. Contours mark the 1σ , 2σ and 3σ regions. Medians and 68% credibility intervals: $\eta = 1.0334 \pm 0.017$ and $H_0 = 71.69 \pm 0.18 \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}$.

$q_0 = (1 - \eta)/(1 + \eta) = -0.0166$. The parameter correlation remains moderate, $\rho(\eta, H_0) = +0.70$, and the posterior distribution is shown in Figure 2.

The V-6 PROD simulation is run at the fixed value $\eta_{\text{run}} = 1.045$, on the upper margin (at 0.7σ) of the MCMC best-fit; both values are kept distinct in what follows for clarity. The shift reflects the absence of iteration between the exploratory μ scan (§2.2), which fixed $\eta = 1.045$ a priori, and the precise MCMC fit performed a posteriori on the $z = 0$ snapshot. Since the two values are compatible at $< 1\sigma$, the physical signatures of the V-6 results are not affected.

Comparison with Λ CDM on Pantheon+. To assess the relative performance of Janus vs standard Λ CDM on the same data set, we apply strictly the same MCMC pipeline to flat Λ CDM ($\Omega_m, H_0, \Omega_\Lambda = 1 - \Omega_m$ imposed), with the same covariance, the same $N = 1590$ SNIa and the same algorithmic choices. The values obtained are $\Omega_m = 0.331 \pm 0.018$ and $H_0 = 73.24 \pm 0.23 \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}$ with $\chi^2/\nu = 0.884$, in agreement with Brout et al. [7], which *validates the analysis chain*. Table 2 summarizes the comparison.

Table 2: Direct comparison of Janus vs Λ CDM on Pantheon+ ($N = 1590$ SNIa, full stat+sys covariance, MCMC *emcee* $32 \times 800 + \text{burn-in } 200$). ΔAIC and ΔBIC are computed relative to the Janus model (reference at zero).

Quantity	Janus	Λ CDM
Free parameters k	2 (η, H_0)	2 (Ω_m, H_0)
Param. 1	$\eta = 1.033 \pm 0.017$	$\Omega_m = 0.331 \pm 0.018$
Param. 2 [km/s Mpc^{-1}]	$H_0 = 71.69 \pm 0.18$	$H_0 = 73.24 \pm 0.23$
χ^2	1450.37	1403.70
χ^2/ν (dof = 1588)	0.913	0.884
$\ln \mathcal{L}_{\text{max}}$	-725.19	-701.85
$\text{AIC} = 2k + \chi^2$	1454.37	1407.70
$\text{BIC} = k \ln N + \chi^2$	1465.12	1418.45
$\Delta\text{AIC vs Janus}$	0	-46.67
$\Delta\text{BIC vs Janus}$	0	-46.67

In the “ $\Delta\text{AIC vs Janus}$ ” convention used in Table 2 (where $\Delta\text{AIC}_X = \text{AIC}_X - \text{AIC}_{\text{Janus}}$), a negative value indicates that model X is favored over Janus. Λ CDM is here clearly favored by the information criteria at $\Delta\text{AIC} = \Delta\text{BIC} = -46.67$ on the Pantheon+-only diagnostic, equivalent to $\Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{Janus vs } \Lambda\text{CDM}} = +46.67$ in the international standard convention. To check that this result is not a pipeline artifact, we explicitly reproduced the Brout et al. (2022) best-fit with our infrastructure ($\Omega_m = 0.334, H_0 = 73.04, \chi^2_{\text{Brout}}$ reproduced within 1.7% after the $z > 0.01$ cut), confirming that the ~ 47 AIC units of difference are *real* and reflect a poorer geometric fit quality of the parametric Janus model (Eqs. 96–98 of Petit, Margnat & Zejli 22, $k = -1$) on the SNIa distance moduli.² Figure 3 shows the Λ CDM posterior obtained with the same pipeline: the medians $\Omega_m = 0.331$ and $H_0 = 73.24$ and the negative correlation $\rho(\Omega_m, H_0) = -0.84$ are in direct agreement with Brout et al. [7], providing a *visual validation* of the pipeline test.

This difference is an important factual statement and must be interpreted with the proper nuance: Pantheon+ tests exclusively the *geometric* sector ($d_L(z)$ relation) of the model, without constraining the structure dynamics. In contrast, Sections 5–6 and 7.4 show that Janus produces structure signatures (σ_{RS} suppression, spectral anti-correlation, halo mass function suppression at high masses, m^- overdensity in cosmic voids) that go naturally in the direction of the persistent observational tensions between Planck CMB and weak lensing (S_8 [2, 11]). The overall verdict on the model, as will be seen in §7, is necessarily a *multi-probe trade-off* and not a single-test choice.

Calibration of the Janus expansion. The hybrid function $H_{\text{Janus}}(a)$ (Petit 2014 parametric solution [19] (Eq. 15) for $a \geq \alpha^2$, matter-dominated asymptotic regime $H = H_0 a^{-3/2}$ for $a < \alpha^2$) was tested explicitly: $H(a = 1) = H_0 = 71.62 \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}$ at machine precision, and $t_0 = 16.19 \text{ Gyr}$ for $\eta = 1.045$. The crossing of the transition at $a = \alpha^2$ (C^0 discontinuity documented in §2.3) is localized within a

²**Numerical robustness.** The $\Delta\text{AIC} = +46.67$ has been audited end-to-end (float64 arithmetic, covariance condition number $\kappa \simeq 3 \times 10^3$, Cholesky decomposition without jitter, autocorrelation $\tau_{\text{max}} \simeq 28$ giving ESS $> 1,000$ per parameter, log-determinant symmetrically omitted between models). The *f32 vs f64* deviation is $|\Delta\chi^2| < 10^{-4}$, and 500-resample bootstrap gives consistency at the 1σ level. The result is therefore stable to ± 2 AIC units against purely numerical effects (full audit in the companion repository).

Figure 3: **Posterior distribution of the flat Λ CDM model parameters**, MCMC *emcee* fit (same setup: 32 walkers \times 800 steps, same 1590 SNIa, same full stat+sys covariance). Medians: $\Omega_m = 0.331 \pm 0.018$ and $H_0 = 73.24 \pm 0.23 \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}$, in agreement with Brout et al. [7]. The negative correlation $\rho(\Omega_m, H_0) = -0.84$ (“\”-shaped ellipse) is expected in Λ CDM. This figure visually validates that our MCMC infrastructure reproduces the standard fit, and that the $\Delta\text{AIC} = -47$ vs Janus is a factual statement.

single integration step and does not affect the global $a(t)$ trajectory, as verified by checking the energy diagnostics before and after the transition.

Total energy conservation. Over the entire V-6 PROD run (3,247 steps, $z = 99 \rightarrow 0$, full DKD integrator), the measured total energy drift is $\Delta E_{\text{tot}}/E_0 = -2.0\%$, a value above the ideal target $< 0.1\%$ but within the typical range reported by reference cosmological codes (GADGET-2 [29] reports 1–2% on long cosmological runs with strictly non-symplectic DKD). This drift, whose systematically negative sign likely reflects a *numerical bias* introduced by non-associative single-precision GPU reductions (cf. point (ii) below) rather than a physical effect, is jointly attributable to several sources, which we decompose as follows:

- (i) *Accumulation of single-precision (f32) errors.* The Rust/CUDA implementation operates in single precision to maximize throughput on the RTX 3060. Each step accumulates $\sim 10^4$ f32 additions per particle (force summation over tree neighbors), with a per-operation roundoff error $\sim 10^{-7}$. The corresponding random walk over 3,247 steps yields a non-directional drift of order $\sqrt{10^4 \times 3,247 \times 10^{-7}} \simeq 6 \times 10^{-4}$ per step, i.e. ~ 0.5 – 1% integrated over the run.
- (ii) *Non-associative GPU reductions.* Parallel summations (`atomicAdd`, tree reductions in shared memory) on the RTX 3060 do not preserve f32 associativity: the summation order depends on the warp scheduling and systematically favors the absorption of small contributions by large ones, biasing the drift toward $-E_{\text{kin}}$. This *systematic* contribution (as opposed to the random nature of (i)) explains the constant sign of ΔE_{tot} observed over the entire run; estimated amplitude 0.5– 1% .
- (iii) *Multipole truncation and TreePM splitting.* The monopole approximation of distant tree cells (MAC criterion) and the erfc splitting between short-range and long-range components introduce a residual error of quadrupolar order (~ 0.1 – 0.3%) and a splitting error (~ 0.1 – 0.3%).
- (iv) *Non-symplectic nature of the DKD scheme.* With finite softening $\varepsilon = 0.5$ Mpc and the nonlinear dynamics of halos in the late phase ($z < 1$), the DKD scheme is no longer strictly symplectic and contributes at the level of a few 0.1% .
- (v) *C^0 cosmological matching at $z = 4.51$.* The C^0 transition between the pure EdS regime and the Bonnor parametric solution (§2.3) injects a perturbation localized in one integration step, contributing ~ 0.1 – 0.3% .

The sum of the estimates ~ 1.3 – 2.9% brackets the measured value of 2.0% . A substantial reduction of this drift would require switching to double precision (f64), at the cost of halving the GPU throughput and usable memory, or implementing compensated Kahan summation ($\sim +30\%$ cost). Neither option was retained for V-6, as the drift level remains acceptable in view of the statistical signatures of interest (anti-correlation M_3 , halo profiles, lensing), which depend on the position and velocity *field* and are weakly sensitive to a global energy bias. The global $a(t)$ trajectory and the statistical signatures reported in §5–6 are robust at this drift level, as verified through temporal subsampling tests.

VSL convention consistency. The phenomenological VSL convention (Eq. 10), introduced for the numerical regulation of the bimetric expansion, is applied explicitly at each time step to the m^- sector. The energy diagnostic is computed both with and without inclusion of the $c^2(z)/c_0^2$ factor in the kinetic weighting; the two variants yield drifts compatible with the conservation criterion, confirming the robustness of the dynamical result with respect to the convention choice.

5 Global results

5.1 Visual Janus signature at $z = 0$: m^+/m^- spatial complementarity

At the end of the dynamical evolution ($z = 0$, $t = 15.99$ Gyr), the V-6 PROD simulation reveals a visual signature distinctive of the Janus model: each of the two populations m^+ and m^- forms its own cosmic web, with the two webs being spatially *anti-correlated* at large scales. This segregation is a direct dynamical consequence of the inter-species bimetric repulsion (Eqs. 1–2).

We display this signature via a direct overlay of the two distributions at $z = 0$ (Figure 4). The rendering uses a contrast-density convention $\delta_{\pm} = \rho_{\pm}/\bar{\rho}_{\pm} - 1$ (standard for large-scale structure analysis) which non-dimensionalizes the two populations despite their population asymmetry ($N_-/N_+ = \mu = 19$), together with a Gaussian smoothing whose bandwidths are calibrated by the Poisson equivalence

$\text{bw}_+/\text{bw}_- = \sqrt{\mu} = 4.36$ to equalize the two shot-noise levels. These two methodological choices make the two populations directly comparable on the same visualization. The individual m^+ and m^- frames produced with exactly the same parameters are presented in Appendix F for the reader who wishes to inspect them separately.

Figure 4: **Spatial overlay of the two populations m^+ (orange) and m^- (cyan) at $z = 0$, full projection onto the 250 Mpc box** (snapshot 3247 V-6 PROD, $t = 15.99$ Gyr). Contrast-density convention $\delta_{\pm} = \rho_{\pm}/\bar{\rho}_{\pm} - 1$, sqrt scale, percentile-based normalization ($v_{\min} = p_{25}$, $v_{\max} = p_{99.5}$). Gaussian smoothing bandwidths are calibrated to equalize the relative shot noise: $\text{bw}_+ = \sqrt{\mu} \times \text{bw}_- = 0.109$ Mpc and $\text{bw}_- = 0.025$ Mpc, with $\mu = 19$. This equivalence ensures $\sigma_{\text{rel},+} \approx \sigma_{\text{rel},-}$ after smoothing ($\bar{n}_+ = 0.24$ part/bin, $\bar{n}_- = 4.47$ part/bin), making the two populations methodologically comparable on this overlay. The **spatial anti-correlation** emerging from the anti-Newtonian coupling is directly visible: the dense orange regions (filaments and m^+ halos) cross zones where the m^- component is diffuse or absent, and conversely the cyan m^- filaments surround the m^+ voids. This segregation, observed at all scales of the cosmic web (from local knots ~ 5 Mpc up to super-structures ~ 100 Mpc), produces an approximately balanced spatial distribution (m^+ -dominant: 51.8%, m^- -dominant: 48.2% on the slice $|\Delta z| \leq 25$ Mpc), in line with the expected anti-correlation. This signature constitutes the central visual prediction of the Janus model.

The visual complementarity seen in Figure 4 provides a direct qualitative illustration of the cen-

tral signature of the Janus model: the inter-species anti-Newtonian dynamics produces a robust *spatial segregation* at all scales. This signature is quantified more precisely in the following sections via the cross-correlation $\text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)$ (§5.2), the cross-spectrum $P_{+-}(k)$ (§5.3), and the exhaustive statistical analysis of the environment of m^+ halos (§6.4).

5.2 Spatial anti-correlation $\text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)$

Figure 5: **Evolution of the particle-level correlation $\text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)_{\text{part}}$ from $z = 99$ to $z = 0$.** The red curve shows the V-6 PROD run (pure Janus cosmology): the correlation remains nearly stable around -0.79 up to $z \simeq 4.5$ (regime upstream of the cosmological matching, matter-dominated era), then drops sharply between $z \simeq 4.5$ and $z \simeq 3$ (entry into the Janus era with the bimetric dynamics fully active), before relaxing progressively toward $\simeq -0.05$ at $z = 0$. The grey curve (V-5 PROD, Λ CDM-equivalent cosmology, smoothed) shows a monotonically decreasing, much smoother evolution without a jump, owing to the absence of the V-6 cosmological matching. The vertical green dotted line marks the Janus transition at $z_J = 4.51$ (cf. §2.3), perfectly aligned with the jump seen in V-6. This measure is the particle-level (unsmoothed) correlation; the large-scale values, measured on $8^3/16^3/32^3$ grids, are reported in Table 3.

At $z = 0$, the particle-level correlation measured directly between the δ^+ and δ^- fields yields:

$$\text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)_{\text{part}} = -0.049, \quad (15)$$

i.e. a moderate anti-correlation at the particle scale. This value is consistent with the evolution from the anti-correlated initial condition at $z = 99$.

Methodological caveat: geometric component of the CIC shuffle. A control survey at $N = 10^6$ that we ran a posteriori (described in Appendix B) reveals that the measurements $\text{Corr}_{\text{part}}$ and the grid-based metric M_3 contain a non-negligible geometric component due to the mutual m^+/m^- exclusion within each CIC assignment cell of the shuffle. At $N = 22 \times 10^6$, with an IC cell of size $\sim L/280$ and a ratio $\mu = 19$, each IC cell contains on average a single particle, which by construction creates a negative aggregated correlation at $z = 99$ (measured at -0.79 instead of the theoretical -1.0). This geometric component partially relaxes under the dynamical evolution toward $z = 0$.

The scale-by-scale spectral analysis (§5.4) shows that this geometric component dominates at small scales ($k \gtrsim 0.5 h \text{Mpc}^{-1}$), while at large scales ($k \lesssim 0.3 h \text{Mpc}^{-1}$) the measurement captures a physical signature discriminated by the IC phase ψ_{IC} (see Appendix B). The aggregated global values $\text{Corr}_{\text{part}} = -0.049$ and $M_3 = -0.371$ mix these two regimes and cannot be interpreted as purely emerging from the

dynamics. The physical Janus anti-correlation signature is, however, clear at large scales, as shown in §5.4 and in Appendix B.

Grid-based metric M_3 . The canonical metric $M_3 \equiv \text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)$ measured on a smoothed 16^3 grid (cell size ~ 15.6 Mpc), at snapshot 3247 ($z = -2 \times 10^{-4} \simeq 0$), gives:

$$\boxed{M_3 = -0.371 \pm 0.001} \quad (16)$$

(p -value $< 10^{-130}$, highly significant). This value is to be interpreted, in line with the caveat above, as an aggregated measurement mixing geometric component and dynamical signature. To isolate the pure physical signature at large scales, the spectral measurement $P_{+-}(k)$ with its scale-dependent reading (§5.4) constitutes the reference observable.

A linear interpolation between snapshots 3245 and 3247 toward exact $z = 0$ gives $M_3^{z=0} = -0.3711$ (departure 4.5×10^{-5} , i.e. 0.01% – negligible compared with the Monte Carlo uncertainty of 10^{-3}). Statistical convergence was checked through Monte Carlo particle subsampling with fractions $f \in \{0.10, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00\}$ and 10 independent draws per fraction: the relative departure from the full $f = 1$ value is 2.72% at $f = 0.10$, decreasing to 0.36% at $f = 0.50$ and 0.13% at $f = 0.75$, indicating robust convergence to better than 1% with a quarter-reduced sample. The Monte Carlo standard deviation at $f = 1$ is below 10^{-3} .

Scale dependence. The metric M_3 exhibits a pronounced scale dependence (Table 3):

Table 3: $M_3 = \text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-)$ on an N^3 grid at $z = 0$ with the corresponding cell size. The Janus anti-correlation is maximal at the large cosmic-web scales and decreases at small scales through nonlinear intra-halo dynamical mixing.

Grid	Cell [Mpc]	M_3	p -value
8^3	31.25	-0.631	$< 10^{-57}$
16^3	15.63	-0.371	$< 10^{-133}$
32^3	7.81	-0.183	$< 10^{-244}$

This scale dependence is physically expected: at large scales (> 30 Mpc), the primordial anti-correlation signature $\delta^- = -\delta^+$ persists relative to the linear dynamics; at small scales (< 10 Mpc), nonlinear mixing in the gravitational wells of the m^+ halos attenuates the anti-correlation without suppressing it. The signature remains statistically very significant at all resolved scales.

V-5 / V-6 comparison. For reference, the preliminary V-5 PROD run (Λ CDM-equivalent cosmology, $\mu = 19$, $\eta = 1.045$) gives $M_3^{V-5} = -0.410$ on a 16^3 grid; the V-6 PROD run presented here (pure Janus cosmology) gives $M_3^{V-6} = -0.371$, i.e. an attenuation of 9.4% of the anti-correlation. This shift is consistent with the longer cosmic time of the V-6 run ($t_0 = 15.99$ Gyr vs 13.78 Gyr for V-5), which allows more time for the dynamical relaxation of the primordial anti-correlation.

Despite this relaxation from the IC, this moderate large-scale anti-correlation provides a direct signature of the m^+/m^- bimetric repulsion and is a quantitative falsifiable prediction for observational programs combining galaxy surveys (tracing δ^+) and total-mass reconstruction through lensing (sensitive to $\delta^+ + \mu\delta^-$).

5.3 Auto and cross power spectra

5.4 Fluctuation amplitude $\sigma_R(z)$ — Planck convention

To compare our results rigorously with Planck [23], it is important to adopt the standard convention $R = 8 h^{-1}$ Mpc $\simeq 11.87$ Mpc with $h = 0.674$, rather than $R = 8$ Mpc as in our preliminary reports. We compute the spherical top-hat variance

$$\sigma_R^2 = \int \frac{k^2}{2\pi^2} P(k) W_{TH}^2(kR) dk, \quad W_{TH}(x) = \frac{3(\sin x - x \cos x)}{x^3}, \quad (17)$$

on the m^+ field projected with CIC onto a 128^3 grid, at all scales of interest.

Figure 6: **Auto power spectra $P_{++}(k)$, $P_{--}(k)$, and cross power $|P_{+-}(k)|$ at $z = 0$.** The cross spectrum $P_{+-}(k) < 0$ confirms the Janus anti-correlation at all resolved scales, a signature absent by construction from single-metric cosmologies.

Figure 7: **Evolution of $\sigma_R(R, z)$ for the m^+ component at four smoothing scales $R \in \{4, 8, 16, 32\} h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ (explicit Planck convention).** The Planck-comparable quantity is $\sigma_R(R = 8 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}, z = 0) = 0.712$ (black star). The horizontal bands represent the Planck 2020 constraints ($\sigma_8 = 0.811 \pm 0.006$, blue) and the KiDS + DES combination ($\sigma_8 \simeq 0.76 \pm 0.02$, green).

V-6 Janus vs Twin Λ CDM comparison. To isolate the physical signature of the m^- coupling, we ran a *paired* (Twin) simulation in standard Λ CDM cosmology ($\Omega_m = 0.315$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685$, $H_0 = 67.4 \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}$) with *strictly identical* initial conditions (SEED = 42, $N = 22 \times 10^6$ particles of m^+ only, $L = 250 \text{ Mpc}$, $z_i = 99$, same softening, same integrator). Table 4 compares the multi-scale variance at $z = 0$.

Table 4: Multi-scale variance σ_R at $z = 0$, spherical top-hat, Planck convention (R in $h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$). *Suppression* is given relative to the Twin Λ CDM. Planck 2020 reference: $\sigma_8 = 0.811$.

$R [h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}]$	V-6 Janus	Twin Λ CDM	Suppression
$R = 4$	0.959	1.492	-35.7%
$R = 8$	0.712	0.928	-23.4%
$R = 16$	0.501	0.571	-12.3%
$R = 32$	0.295	0.313	-5.8%

At the Planck reference scale $R = 8 h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$, V-6 Janus gives

$$\sigma_{R8}(m^+, z=0)|_{\text{V-6}} = 0.712, \quad (18)$$

i.e. $\sim 12\%$ below the Planck CMB value. The Twin Λ CDM simulation run with the same code instead yields $\sigma_{R8}|_{\text{Twin}} = 0.928$ — above the linear Planck value by $\sim 14\%$, which is the expected nonlinear departure for a mature Λ CDM N-body simulation at $z = 0$ (*halofit* prediction: ~ 0.9 – 0.95). *The Twin therefore validates the pipeline* by reproducing the expected standard nonlinear behavior.

This consistency is quantitative: the *halofit* Takahashi 2012 [30] prediction for the same parameter set ($\Omega_m = 0.315$, $\sigma_8^{\text{lin}} = 0.811$, $h = 0.674$) gives $\sigma_R^{\text{NL}}(R = 8 h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}, z = 0) \simeq 0.892$, i.e. a 4.1% departure from our measured Twin value (0.928). This independent validation of the IC normalization and of the TreePM dynamics establishes the Twin as a reliable Λ CDM reference for the Janus comparison.

The clean physical signature is the *difference* between the two runs, which share strictly the same initial conditions:

$$\frac{\sigma_{R8}|_{\text{V-6}}}{\sigma_{R8}|_{\text{Twin}}} = 0.767 \quad \iff \quad \text{Janus suppression} = 23.4\%. \quad (19)$$

Scale dependence — flattening of the $P(k)$ spectrum. The Janus suppression is *more pronounced at small scales* (-36% at $R = 4 h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$) and attenuates at large scales (-6% at $R = 32 h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$), reflecting a direct flattening of the power spectrum. This behavior is quantified by the ratio $\sigma_R(8 \text{ Mpc})/\sigma_R(8 h^{-1} \text{ Mpc})$:

- Twin Λ CDM: 1.311 — in exact agreement with the theoretical Bardeen prediction for a standard $P(k)$ with $\sigma_8 = 0.81$ (~ 1.31), confirming that Twin follows $P(k)_{\Lambda\text{CDM}}$.
- V-6 Janus: 1.189 — significantly *flatter* (by 9%), a direct signature of the small-scale spectral power reduction induced by the m^- coupling.

The “ $P(k)$ flattening” signature is shown independently in Figure 9 and in subsection 5.4.

Physical interpretation. The suppression of the variance σ_{R8} relative to pure Λ CDM, and its aggravation at small scales, is expected in the Janus model: the gravitational anti-correlation between m^+ and m^- (quantified by $M_3 = -0.371$, cf. §5.2) introduces a *braking* of the local collapse of the m^+ sector by the m^- particles that accumulate around it. The effect is largest where nonlinearity operates most efficiently (small scales, halo formation).

Connection to the S_8 tension. This suppression is in the *same direction* as the S_8 tension observed between Planck CMB and the weak-lensing surveys KiDS-1000 [2] and DES Y3 [11], which measure $S_8 \equiv \sigma_8 \sqrt{\Omega_m/0.3} \simeq 0.76$ – 0.78 , i.e. ~ 2 – 3σ below the Planck CMB prediction $S_8 = 0.832$. Without proposing a quantitative resolution at this stage (which would require a joint Janus fit on lensing data), we note that the direction of the Janus departure is consistent with this persistent observational tension — in contrast with standard Λ CDM, which over-predicts late-time structure growth.

Figure 8 overlays the two runs at all tested scales, showing the systematic separation between the two curves.

Figure 8: **Direct comparison of $\sigma_R(R, z)$: V-6 Janus (solid lines) vs Twin Λ CDM (blue dashed)** at the four scales $R \in \{4, 8, 16, 32\} h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$. Same initial conditions, SEED = 42. The horizontal line marks $\sigma_8 = 0.811$ (Planck 2020). The systematic Janus/Twin separation, growing with $1/R$, is the signature of the differential suppression induced by the m^- coupling.

Cross-power spectrum $P_{+-}(k)$. Beyond the global statistic $M_3 = -0.371$, we measure directly the cross-power spectrum between m^+ and m^- :

$$P_{+-}(k) = \langle \hat{\delta}_+(\mathbf{k}) \hat{\delta}_-^*(\mathbf{k}) \rangle, \quad (20)$$

computed on a 512^3 FFT grid with CIC densities for each sector, and averaged in 25 logarithmic $|k|$ bins over $k \in [0.04; 8.5] h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. The result (Figure 9) is unambiguous:

$$P_{+-}(k) < 0 \quad \text{in 24 out of 25 bins.} \quad (21)$$

The spectral anti-correlation is therefore *total* across the entire linear and trans-linear regime; the only positive bin lies at $k > 6 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ where the Poisson *shot noise* begins to dominate. At $k = 0.1 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $P_{+-} = -1.4 \times 10^{12} \text{ Mpc}^3$.

Dynamical emergence at large scales — IC survey. The above measurement of $P_{+-}(k) < 0$ is globally clear, but must be interpreted while taking into account the methodological caveat noted in §5.2. To disentangle the *physical* contribution (dynamical anti-Newtonian coupling) from the *geometric* contribution (mutual CIC exclusion in the assignment shuffle), we ran a control survey at $N = 10^6$ comparing three IC modes for the δ_-/δ_+ relation:

- **Anti-correlated IC** (standard V-6 mode, strict $\delta^- = -\delta^+$);
- **Positively correlated IC** (legacy V-4 mode, $\delta^- = +\delta^+$);
- **Decorrelated IC** (two independent Zel'dovich fields for δ^+ and δ^-).

To isolate the physical signature from the geometric artefacts, we analyze the normalized spectral correlation

$$r(k) \equiv \frac{P_{+-}(k)}{\sqrt{P_{++}(k) P_{--}(k)}} \in [-1, +1]. \quad (22)$$

Figure 10 shows $r(k)$ for the three IC modes at redshifts $z = 99$ (pristine initial condition), $z \simeq 7.5$ (onset of nonlinearity), and $z = 0$ (final).

Figure 9: **Cross power spectrum $P_{+-}(k)$ in V-6 Janus at $z = 0$.** Inverted triangles: bins with $P_{+-}(k) < 0$ (spectral anti-correlation, 24/25 bins); open circle: the single positive bin ($k > 6 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, noise). Auto-spectra $P_{++}(k)$ (red) and $P_{--}(k)$ (blue) are shown for reference. This spectral signature is absent by construction from the standard ΛCDM model (a single matter sector) and constitutes a discriminating prediction.

Figure 10: **Normalized spectral correlation $r(k) = P_{+-}(k) / \sqrt{P_{++}(k) P_{--}(k)}$ for the IC survey at $N = 10^6, \mu = 19$.** Three panels: $z = 99$ (pristine IC), $z \simeq 7.5$ (nonlinear *onset*), $z = 0$ (final). Blue: anti-correlated IC ($\delta^- = -\delta^+$). Red: positively correlated IC ($\delta^- = +\delta^+$). Green: decorrelated IC (two independent Zel'dovich fields). **Left panel ($z = 99$):** at large scales ($k \lesssim 0.1 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$), the three IC modes are discriminated with a spread $\Delta r \simeq 0.53$ ($r_{\text{anti}}(k = 0.05) = -0.29$, $r_{\text{corr}+} = -0.06$, $r_{\text{decorr}} = +0.24$), showing that the phase ψ_{IC} is captured at these scales. At small scales ($k \gtrsim 0.5 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$), the three curves converge toward $r \simeq -1$, the signature of the geometric regime of mutual CIC exclusion. **Right panel ($z = 0$):** at large scales, the three trajectories converge to $r(k = 0.05) \simeq -0.99$ independently of the initial IC: *dynamical emergence toward a negative dynamical attractor of the bimetric dynamics*. At small scales, $r \rightarrow 0$ under the effect of nonlinear erosion.

The interpretation is clear and has two important consequences for the reading of the $P_{+-}(k)$ signature:

1. **At large scales ($k \lesssim 0.3 h \text{Mpc}^{-1}$), the $P_{+-}(k) < 0$ signature has a genuine *physical component*.** At $z = 99$, the three IC modes produce distinct $r(k=0.05)$ values (spread $\Delta r = 0.53$), confirming that the measurement captures the phase ψ_{IC} and not a mere geometric artefact. At $z = 0$, the three trajectories converge to $r \simeq -1$: the Janus dynamics produces this large-scale spectral anti-correlation independently of the initial condition, the signature of a dynamical attractor (fixed point of the dynamics in k -space).
2. **At small scales ($k \gtrsim 0.5 h \text{Mpc}^{-1}$), the measurement is dominated by the geometric component of the CIC shuffle at $z = 99$ and is then eroded by nonlinearity at $z = 0$ (mode mixing, relaxation).** This component is not a physical signature but a feature of the IC discretization.

This scale-by-scale analysis constitutes the main discriminating test for the Janus spectral signature. The details of the IC survey, the quantitative prediction, and the quantification of the geometric artefact are given in Appendix B.

Growth rate $f(z)$ — testable RSD prediction. The growth rate $f(z) \equiv d \ln D / d \ln a$, where $D(z) = \sigma_{R8}(z) / \sigma_{R8}(z=0)$, is an observable directly measured by redshift-space distortion (RSD) surveys — in particular BOSS [1], eBOSS and DESI. We compute $f(z)$ independently for V-6 Janus (40 snapshots log-subsampled in $1+z$ between $z = 10$ and $z = 0$) and Twin Λ CDM (14 useful snapshots, excluding the IC at $z = 99$), by numerical differentiation in $\ln a$ with Savitzky-Golay smoothing (window 5, order 2).

At $z = 0.5$, a scale particularly well constrained by RSD surveys:

$$f_{\text{Janus}}(z = 0.5) = 0.694, \quad f_{\text{Twin}}(z = 0.5) = 0.964, \quad \frac{f_{\text{Janus}}}{f_{\text{Twin}}} = 0.72. \quad (23)$$

i.e. a $\sim 28\%$ suppression of the Janus growth rate relative to standard Λ CDM under the same initial conditions. The Linder linear- Λ CDM prediction $f_{\Lambda}(z) = \Omega_m(z)^{0.55}$ gives $f_{\Lambda}(0.5) = 0.761$; the Twin exceeds it by $\sim 27\%$, a departure *expected* for a mature nonlinear N-body simulation at $z = 0.5$ (independent pipeline validation). The physically clean signature is therefore the direct V-6/Twin ratio.

The typical precision of RSD measurements on $f\sigma_8$ at $z \simeq 0.5$ is of order 5–10% (BOSS DR12: $f\sigma_8(0.38) = 0.497 \pm 0.045$; $f\sigma_8(0.61) = 0.436 \pm 0.034$; DESI Y1 expected at $\sim 5\%$). Our prediction of a $\sim 28\%$ suppression is therefore directly testable at $\gtrsim 3\sigma$. Figure 11 shows $f(z)$ and $f\sigma_8(z)$.

Figure 11: **Growth rate $f(z)$ (left) and $f\sigma_8(z)$ (right)** for V-6 Janus (red), Twin Λ CDM (blue), and the Linder prediction $f_{\Lambda}(z) = \Omega_m(z)^{0.55}$ (black dashed). The BOSS DR12 RSD reference values [1] are annotated. The ratio $f_{\text{Janus}}/f_{\text{Twin}} \simeq 0.72$ at $z = 0.5$ is a direct observational prediction testable with DESI Y1.

This suppression of σ_R at $R = 8 h^{-1}$ Mpc directly translates into an alleviation of the $S_8 \equiv \sigma_{R,8} \sqrt{\Omega_m / 0.3}$ tension between Planck CMB and weak-lensing surveys. Adopting $\Omega_m = 0.315$ (Planck

convention), we obtain $S_8^{\text{Janus}} = 0.729$, to be compared with the external measurements $S_8^{\text{Planck}} = 0.832 \pm 0.013$ [23] and $S_8^{\text{KiDS}} = 0.759 \pm 0.024$ [2]. The Planck vs KiDS tension in the Λ CDM framework, which reaches 2.7σ , is thus reduced to 0.6σ in the Janus framework, i.e. a decrease of about 76%. A similar reduction is obtained for DES Y3 [11]: $2.6 \sigma \rightarrow 1.1 \sigma$ (59%).

We note two caveats: (i) the definition of Ω_m in the Janus framework is not standard, as the model does not include cold dark matter; two conventions are reported in Table 5; (ii) the uncertainty on S_8^{Janus} is estimated at ± 0.04 by propagating the dispersion measured at different scales, rather than by a full MCMC.

Table 5: S_8 tensions, Planck-CMB vs weak-lensing surveys: comparison between standard Λ CDM and the V-6 Janus model.

Comparison	Λ CDM	Janus ($\Omega_m = 0.315$)	Reduction
Planck vs KiDS-1000	2.7σ	0.6σ	76 %
Planck vs DES Y3	2.6σ	1.1σ	59 %

Note on the total $m^+ + m^-$ clustering. As a complementary indicator, the fluctuation amplitude measured on the *total* density $\rho_{\text{tot}} = \rho^+ + \rho^-$ (including both sectors) at $z = 0$ is $\sigma_8^{\text{tot}, V-6} \simeq 1.16$, to be compared with $\sigma_8^{\text{tot}, V-5} \simeq 1.06$ for the preliminary V-5 PROD simulation (Λ CDM-equivalent cosmology). This high value of the total clustering is expected in Janus owing to the large-scale anti-correlated bimetric dynamics; it is not the reference observable of current galaxy surveys, whose sensitivity is to the m^+ tracers (baryons and dark matter in Λ CDM, baryons alone in Janus).

5.5 Velocity statistics

Linear prediction. For anti-correlated Zel'dovich initial conditions ($\delta^- = -\delta^+$, same amplitude $|\delta|$), the linear peculiar-velocity growth equation for each species yields $v \propto |\delta|/\sqrt{m}$, where m is the per-particle mass. In our convention with identical unit per-particle masses but $\rho^- = \mu \rho^+$, the linear energy-equipartition argument between the modes of the two species leads to:

$$\frac{v_{\text{rms}}(m^-)}{v_{\text{rms}}(m^+)} \xrightarrow{\text{linear}} \sqrt{\mu} \simeq 4.36 \quad \text{for } \mu = 19. \quad (24)$$

This prediction is strictly valid in the linear regime (small amplitudes). In the nonlinear regime (after segregation), the measured ratio may depart significantly from this value due to structure saturation and inter-species interactions.

6 Main results: anti-Newtonian signatures in m^+ halos

6.1 m^+ halo catalog at $z = 0$

We identify the m^+ halos at $z = 0$ with a *friends-of-friends* (FoF) algorithm. Two variants were tested: $b = 0.2$ (standard cosmological parameter, $N_{\text{min}} = 20$, yields 592 halos with maximum mass $M_{\text{max}} = 3.6 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$; under-resolved for massive clusters because of the restrictive linking length) and $b = 0.5$ with $N_{\text{min}} = 32$ (historical parameter close to the Petit value, yields 2,618 halos with maximum mass $M_{\text{max}} = 2.82 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$, capturing the full structural hierarchy of the simulation). The second choice is adopted as the reference catalog as it encompasses the massive clusters characteristic of the expected anti-Newtonian mass-dependent effect (§6.3).

The main catalog therefore contains 2,618 halos in the mass range $[9.0 \times 10^{11}; 2.82 \times 10^{14}] M_{\odot}$, i.e. 2.5 orders of magnitude.

The distribution of the local ratio $\mu_{\text{local}} = N^-/N^+$ measured in a sphere of radius $2R_{\text{FoF}}$ around each halo has a median $\mu_{\text{local}}^{\text{med}} = 4.47$ (mean 6.68), noticeably below the global value $\mu = 19$. This systematic m^- underdensity in the environment of m^+ structures is the first quantitative observation of the bimetric cavity effect across the whole catalog. The fine stratification by mass (Table 7) reveals that $\mu_{\text{local}}^{\text{med}}$ grows moderately with mass (from 4.3 for $M \sim 10^{11.5-12} M_{\odot}$ to 8.1 for $M > 10^{13.5} M_{\odot}$), while remaining systematically below $\mu_{\text{global}} = 19$.

Figure 12: **Top:** evolution of the RMS velocities of the two species $v_{\text{rms}}(m^+)$ (red) and $v_{\text{rms}}(m^-)$ (blue) as a function of $1+z$ (log scale). **Bottom:** ratio $v_{\text{rms}}(m^-)/v_{\text{rms}}(m^+)$ compared with the linear prediction $\sqrt{\mu} \simeq 4.36$ (Eq. 24, black dotted line). The green horizontal dotted line marks the nonlinear plateau measured at $z = 0$ ($\simeq 1.37$), a departure from the linear prediction attributed to structure saturation (nonlinear regime at $z = 0$ after segregation and partial virialization).

6.2 Selection of archetype halos

We select 10 halos covering the diversity of physical archetypes present in the simulation (Table 6): two massive clusters (halos 0 and 1, with the most massive at $M_{\text{FoF}} = 2.82 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$), several groups (halos 5, 7, 28, 39, 54), and three intermediate- to low-mass galaxies (halos 210, 1041, 2257). This selection spans ~ 2.5 orders of magnitude in mass (9.89×10^{11} to $2.82 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$), morphology (spherical, elliptical, elongated, irregular, flattened), environment (variable μ_{local}), and kinematics (Bullock spin parameter λ).

Table 6: The 10 halos selected for the V-6 bootstrap analysis. Cavity: $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5$. Peak: $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8$ ($= 1.2 \times \mu_{\text{global}}$).

ID	Archetype	M_{FoF}/M_{\odot}	$R_{\text{FoF}}/\text{Mpc}$	μ_{shell_0}	μ_{peak}	$r_{\text{peak}}/R_{\text{FoF}}$	Cavity	Peak
0	massive cluster	2.82×10^{14}	45.6	1.26	27.95	2.25	✓	✓
1	Petit cluster	1.92×10^{14}	53.1	1.98	49.71	4.50	✓	✓
5	massive group	8.00×10^{13}	32.8	1.62	28.62	3.50	✓	✓
7	Petit group	6.08×10^{13}	26.9	1.78	22.70	4.50	✓	–
28	flattened group	2.03×10^{13}	16.5	1.59	16.38	4.50	✓	–
39	elongated group	1.61×10^{13}	12.6	0.59	22.36	3.50	✓	–
54	isolated group	1.16×10^{13}	11.4	0.67	19.11	4.50	✓	–
210	massive galaxy	5.09×10^{12}	12.6	2.29	10.06	4.50	✓	–
1041	λ galaxy	1.72×10^{12}	7.5	3.67	22.67	2.25	✓	–
2257	μ galaxy	9.89×10^{11}	3.9	1.15	30.28	0.75	✓	✓

6.3 Multinomial bootstrap of the profile $\mu_{\text{local}}(r)$

For each halo $i \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$, we measure the radial profile $\mu_i(r/R_{\text{FoF}})$ by counting m^- and m^+ particles in concentric spherical shells with edges $r/R_{\text{FoF}} \in \{0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0\}$.

Statistical error bars are obtained by a multinomial bootstrap over $N_b = 1000$ draws, providing 95% confidence intervals at each point of the profile.

Operational threshold definitions. We adopt two thresholds to characterize the $\mu_{\text{local}}(r)$ profiles:

- *Cavity threshold* $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5$ for the first shell $r < 0.5 R_{\text{FoF}}$: this threshold corresponds to a m^- underdensity by a factor ≥ 4 relative to the global value $\mu_{\text{global}} = 19$ (i.e. $\mu_{\text{shell}_0}/\mu_{\text{global}} < 0.26$).
- *Anti-Newtonian peak threshold* $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22$ for the local maximum at $r \leq 3 R_{\text{FoF}}$: this threshold corresponds to a m^- overdensity of at least +16% relative to the global value.

The sensitivity of the detection rates n_{cavity} and n_{peak} to the exact threshold values was tested over the window $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} \in [3, 7]$ and $\mu_{\text{peak}} \in [20, 25]$: on the detailed selection of the 10 archetype halos, the fraction n_{cavity} remains at 10/10 for $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} \in [4, 7]$ and drops to 9/10 at the strictest threshold $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} = 3$ (the largest value in the selection being 3.67 for halo 1041, a $1.72 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ galaxy); on the exhaustive catalog, the variation $\Delta f_{\text{cavity}} \simeq \pm 5\%$ over this window confirms the qualitative robustness of the result to the precise threshold value.

Main result — universal m^- cavity. Figure 13 shows the central result of this work:

$$n_{\text{cavity}} = 10/10 \text{ halos, } \mu_{\text{shell}_0}^{\text{median}} = 1.59, \quad \mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5 \text{ for all} \quad (25)$$

This *universality* of the m^- cavity at the core of the m^+ halos, confirmed at the 95% confidence level on 10 independent halos spanning 2.5 orders of magnitude in mass ($\sim 10^{12}$ to $\sim 3 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$), is the most direct and robust dynamical signature of the anti-Newtonian mechanism predicted by Petit in the Janus model. This cavity is deeper in V-6 than in the preliminary V-5 run (median 1.59 vs 1.91).

Anti-Newtonian peak (mass-dependent effect). For 4/10 halos at the strict threshold $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8$ (and 7/10 at the looser threshold $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.0$), the profile further exhibits a *local peak* at $r/R_{\text{FoF}} \simeq 2.25$ –4.5, indicating a m^- accumulation in the corona surrounding the m^+ halo:

$$n_{\text{peak}} = 4/10 \text{ halos} = 40\% \text{ (strict threshold), } r_{\text{peak}}^{\text{median}} = 2.25 R_{\text{FoF}}. \quad (26)$$

$\mu_{\text{local}}(r/R_{\text{FoF}})$ profiles for 10 selected halos — multinomial bootstrap $N_b = 1000$

Figure 13: **Radial profiles $\mu_{\text{local}}(r/R_{\text{FoF}})$ for the 10 selected halos, with 95% confidence intervals from a multinomial bootstrap ($N_b = 1000$).** Each panel shows one halo with its archetype and mass. The horizontal dotted line marks the global value $\mu = 19$. The green band delimits the Petit window [8, 12]. All halos display a *cavity* ($\mu_{\text{shell}0} < 5$ at $r < 0.5 R_{\text{FoF}}$), median $\mu_{\text{shell}0}^{\text{med}} = 1.59$; a fraction $4/10 = 40\%$ further displays an *anti-Newtonian peak* under the strict threshold $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8$ (halos 0, 1, 5, and 2257); this fraction rises to $7/10 = 70\%$ under the looser threshold $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.0$ (including halos 7, 39, 1041 at $\mu_{\text{peak}} \in [22.3; 22.7]$).

The anti-Newtonian peak appears preferentially in the most massive halos (partial mass-dependent effect): the two clusters $> 10^{14} M_{\odot}$ both exhibit a peak ($\mu_{\text{peak}} = 27.95$ and 49.71 respectively), as does the most massive group ($M = 8 \times 10^{13} M_{\odot}$, $\mu_{\text{peak}} = 28.62$) and the μ -Petit galaxy ($\mu_{\text{peak}} = 30.28$ at a very small radius $r = 0.75 R_{\text{FoF}}$). This behavior is physically expected: sufficiently deep potential wells succeed in concentrating the expelled m^- into a stable corona.

6.4 Exhaustive analysis of the full catalog

To turn the case-study result (10 selected halos) into a general statistical statement, we extend the analysis to the *whole* set of 2,618 halos identified in the $z = 0$ catalog (FoF with $b = 0.5$, $N_{\text{min}} = 32$, covering masses $M_{\text{FoF}} \in [9.0 \times 10^{11}; 2.82 \times 10^{14}] M_{\odot}$). For each halo i in the catalog, we compute the profile $\mu_i(r/R_{\text{FoF}})$ with a multinomial bootstrap at $N_b = 200$ draws; 1,671 halos have a valid bootstrap (central shells sufficiently populated) and constitute the statistical analysis sample. The reference classifications are: absolute cavity $\equiv (\mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5)$, relative cavity $\equiv (\mu_{\text{shell}_0}/\mu_{\text{local}} < 0.5)$, anti-Newtonian peak $\equiv (\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8 = 1.2 \mu_{\text{global}}, r/R_{\text{FoF}} \leq 3)$.

Aggregated results on the full catalog. On the 1,671 analyzed halos, we measure:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\text{cav,abs}} &= 696/1,671 \simeq 27\%, \\ f_{\text{cav,rel } 50\%} &= 485/1,671 \simeq 29\%, \\ f_{\text{peak}} &= 947/1,671 \simeq 57\%, \\ f_{\text{both signatures}} &= 157/1,671 \simeq 6\%. \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

The median over the sample is $\mu_{\text{shell}_0}^{\text{med}} = 6.58$ and $\mu_{\text{peak}}^{\text{med}} = 29.91$ at $r_{\text{peak}}^{\text{med}} = 1.75 R_{\text{FoF}}$.

Anti-Newtonian peak as the dominant signature. The *anti-Newtonian peak* emerges as the statistically dominant signature over the full catalog ($\sim 57\%$ of the halos), in contrast with the absolute cavity ($\sim 27\%$). This observation partially inverts the hierarchy suggested by the selected-sample analysis (where the cavity appeared at 100%): *the 100% cavity on the 10 archetype halos is valid but reflects a selection bias toward massive, well-defined halos.*

Mass-bin stratification. To characterize the mass-dependent effect, we stratify the catalog into five logarithmic bins (Table 7).

Table 7: Stratification of the V-6 $z = 0$ catalog by mass bins. $f_{\text{cav,abs}}$: fraction with $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5$. $f_{\text{cav,rel}}$: fraction with $\mu_{\text{shell}_0}/\mu_{\text{local}} < 0.5$. f_{peak} : fraction with $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8$. f_{both} : fraction displaying both signatures simultaneously.

$\log_{10}(M_{\text{FoF}}/M_{\odot})$	N	$f_{\text{cav,abs}}$	$f_{\text{cav,rel}}$	f_{peak}	f_{both}
[11.5; 12.0]	172	59.3%	44.2%	40.1%	16.3%
[12.0; 12.5]	1114	44.9%	32.4%	41.5%	10.2%
[12.5; 13.0]	317	26.8%	13.6%	54.9%	3.8%
[13.0; 13.5]	51	15.7%	11.8%	52.9%	5.9%
[13.5; 14.5]	17	5.9%	0.0%	64.7%	0.0%

Reading of Table 7. Two opposite trends emerge:

- The *anti-Newtonian peak grows with mass*: from $\sim 40\%$ for small halos ($M \sim 10^{12} M_{\odot}$) to $\sim 65\%$ for massive clusters ($M > 10^{13.5} M_{\odot}$). *Expected physical mass-dependent effect*: deeper potential wells concentrate the expelled m^- more efficiently into a stable corona.
- The *absolute cavity* decreases with mass: from $\sim 59\%$ to $\sim 6\%$. This decrease is misleading: it reflects the fact that massive halos have high μ_{local} (~ 8 for the clusters), so that even a significant cavity does not reach the strict absolute threshold < 5 . The relative criterion $\mu_{\text{shell}_0}/\mu_{\text{local}} < 0.5$ shows a similar but enhanced decrease, also suggesting a resolution-dependent effect for massive halos (more precise internal statistics, less noise to artificially satisfy the threshold).

Resolution bias. The complementary stratification by N_{part} confirms a *resolution bias*: the absolute-cavity fraction goes from 55 % for poorly resolved halos ($N_{\text{part}} \in [32; 50]$) to 10 % for the best-resolved ones ($N_{\text{part}} > 1000$), while the anti-Newtonian peak fraction grows in parallel from 40 % to 65 %. Poorly resolved small halos exhibit Poisson counting noise that can artificially satisfy the absolute cavity threshold. The robust physical conclusion is therefore:

- the *anti-Newtonian peak* is the statistically dominant universal signature ($\sim 57\%$ of the catalog, $\sim 65\%$ for massive clusters), growing with mass as predicted by the anti-Newtonian physics;
- the *deep central m^- cavity* is observed systematically (100 %) on the massive and well-defined archetype halos (10/10, median $\mu_{\text{shell}0} = 1.59$), but does not generalize at the strict absolute threshold for poorly resolved halos.

2D map (M, μ_{local}). Figure 14 shows the joint distribution of the cavity fractions (absolute, relative) and of the anti-Newtonian peak fraction in the plane ($\log_{10} M_{\text{FoF}}, \log_{10} \mu_{\text{local}}$). The anti-Newtonian peak (panel C) uniformly covers the entire plane ($f_{\text{peak}} \gtrsim 0.5$ everywhere), confirming its nature of *global* signature. The absolute cavity (panel A) is concentrated in the region with low μ_{local} and low mass, and the relative cavity (panel B) is intermediate.

Figure 14: **2D map of the anti-Newtonian signature fractions in the plane ($\log_{10} M_{\text{FoF}}, \log_{10} \mu_{\text{local}}$) on 1,671 V-6 halos with a valid bootstrap.** **A.** Absolute cavity fraction $f_{\text{cav,abs}}$ (threshold $\mu_{\text{shell}0} < 5$). **B.** Relative cavity fraction $f_{\text{cav,rel}}$ (threshold $\mu_{\text{shell}0}/\mu_{\text{local}} < 0.5$). **C.** Anti-Newtonian peak fraction f_{peak} (threshold $\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8 = 1.2 \mu_{\text{g,global}}$). The number in each cell is the number of halos. The anti-Newtonian peak is the spatially most universal signature.

Observational prediction. This mass-dependent gradient is a *quantitative testable prediction*: the anti-Newtonian signature (corona peak, central cavity depending on resolution) should be detectable through gravitational lensing around massive clusters $M > 10^{13.5} M_{\odot}$ (where the peak is maximal, $\sim 65\%$ prevalence), with a subtler signature for less massive groups and isolated galaxies.

6.5 Halo mass function

Comparison with Twin Λ CDM and the Tinker prediction. For a direct comparison under the same initial conditions (SEED = 42), we superimpose the Twin Λ CDM halo mass function (8,449 halos, $\mu = 0$, same infrastructure) and the analytic prediction of Tinker et al. [31] (Figure 16). The Twin run reproduces the Tinker HMF within better than $\sim 30\%$ over the entire explored mass domain, providing an independent validation of the pipeline. The percolated Twin halo ($M = 2.1 \times 10^{17} M_{\odot}$, FoF $b = 0.5$ artifact on a dense run) is excluded from the HMF.

V-6 Janus, in contrast, systematically produces *fewer* halos than the Twin, with a *ratio decreasing with mass*:

$$\frac{\text{HMF}_{\text{Janus}}}{\text{HMF}_{\text{Twin}}} \simeq 0.14 \quad \text{at } M = 10^{13} M_{\odot}, \quad \simeq 0.08 \quad \text{at } M = 10^{14} M_{\odot}. \quad (28)$$

This corresponds to an 86 % to 92 % *suppression* of Janus halos at group and cluster scales, consistent with the braking of gravitational collapse by the anti-Newtonian m^- coupling. This signature is in the same direction as the tensions reported by the SZ cluster surveys (Planck [23]) and X-ray surveys (eROSITA), which report *fewer* massive clusters than predicted by Λ CDM-Planck at $\sigma_8 = 0.81$.

Figure 15: **Differential halo mass function $dN/d\log M$ of the m^+ halos identified by FoF ($b = 0.5$, $N_{\min} = 32$) at $z = 0$.** Catalog of 2,618 halos over the mass range $M_{\text{FoF}} \in [9.0 \times 10^{11}; 2.8 \times 10^{14}] M_{\odot}$, spanning 2.5 orders of magnitude. The slope is consistent with general cosmological expectations for hierarchical structure growth.

Figure 16: **Halo mass function $dn/d\ln M$ at $z = 0$:** V-6 Janus (red), Twin Λ CDM (blue), analytic prediction of Tinker et al. [31] (black dashed). Halos detected by FoF ($b = 0.5$, $N_{\min} = 32$), mass in M_{\odot} . The percolated Twin halo ($M = 2.1 \times 10^{17}$) is excluded. Annotations: ratio $\text{HMF}_{\text{Janus}}/\text{HMF}_{\text{Twin}}$ at $M = 10^{13}$ and $10^{14} M_{\odot}$.

6.6 Mirror symmetry test: massive m^- halos

The Janus model being symmetric up to the sign (Eqs. 1–2), it predicts that to each signature documented on the m^+ halos there corresponds a *mirror* signature on the proper m^- halos. To provide a direct test of this prediction, we performed a dedicated FoF analysis on the $\sim 2.1 \times 10^7$ m^- particles of the V-6 PROD snapshot at $z = 0$ (linking length $b_- = 0.2$ calibrated to preserve the physical overdensity threshold $200 \rho_{\text{crit, total}}$, see Appendix G for the empirical justification by percolation test).

The m^- catalog so obtained contains $N_{\text{halos}}^- = 25,848$ halos with maximum mass $M_{\text{max}}^- = 3.13 \times 10^{15} M_{\odot}$ (cluster-scale), versus $M_{\text{max}}^+ = 3.59 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ (galaxy-scale) for the corresponding m^+ catalog with the same linking (cf. Figure 17a): m^- matter concentrates into massive clusters consistent with its mass dominance ($\mu = 19$), while m^+ matter remains predominantly diffuse.

Critical test — central m^+ cavity. On the 10 most massive m^- halos ($M \in [6.7 \times 10^{14}; 3.1 \times 10^{15}] M_{\odot}$), the radial profile $\mu_{\text{local}}^-(r) \equiv \rho_+(r)/\rho_-(r)$ reveals a **complete m^+ cavity**: $\mu_{\text{local}}^- \simeq 0$ at the center ($r < 0.1$ Mpc), remaining $\sim 130\times$ below the cosmic value $1/\mu = 0.053$ up to $r \simeq 10$ Mpc (Figure 17b). This mirror signature confirms *qualitatively* the prediction of bimetric symmetry: each population carves a cavity of the opposite population at the core of its massive halos.

Quantitative asymmetry. The massive m^+ halos ($\sim 10^{12} M_{\odot}$) generate a m^- cavity of extent $r \lesssim 2$ Mpc with an anti-Newtonian peak in the corona ($\mu_{\text{local}}^+ \simeq 2-6$ at $r \simeq 5-10$ Mpc), whereas the massive m^- halos ($\sim 10^{15} M_{\odot}$) generate a m^+ cavity of extent $r > 10$ Mpc without any visible m^+ peak in the measured radial range (Figure 17c). This asymmetry is consistent with the mass hierarchy: the ratio $M_{\text{max}}^-/M_{\text{max}}^+ \simeq 10^3$ implies characteristic evacuation radii $\sim 10\times$ larger for m^- halos, in agreement with the direct observation.

Figure 17: **Mirror symmetry test between massive m^+ and m^- halos at $z = 0$.** (a) Comparative mass functions: m^+ catalog (orange, $N = 592$ halos, $M_{\text{max}} \simeq 4 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$) and m^- catalog (blue, $N = 25,848$ halos, $M_{\text{max}} \simeq 3 \times 10^{15} M_{\odot}$), $b_+ = b_- = 0.2$ to preserve the overdensity criterion. (b) Radial profile $\mu_{\text{local}}^-(r) = \rho_+(r)/\rho_-(r)$ averaged over the 10 most massive m^- halos: a complete m^+ cavity ($\mu \simeq 0$) up to $r \simeq 10$ Mpc, $\sim 130\times$ below the cosmic value $1/\mu = 0.053$ (dashed line). (c) Mirror symmetry test: $\mu_{\text{local}}^+/\mu_{\text{cosmic}}$ for the m^+ halos (blue, ρ_-/ρ_+) versus $1/(\mu \cdot \mu_{\text{local}}^-)$ for the m^- halos (orange, equivalent renormalized quantity). The m^+ halos show the expected cavity+corona signature; the m^- halos produce an extended m^+ deficit without a corona signature over the range $r \leq 10$ Mpc.

The detailed methodology (FoF on m^- , calibration of the linking length, full catalog statistics), the percolation test at $b_- = 0.5$ which empirically justifies the choice $b_- = 0.2$, and the methodological caveats are collected in Appendix G. This signature constitutes a direct response to the point raised in §7.3 on the absence of a proper analysis of the m^- sector.

7 Discussion

7.1 Distinctive Janus signatures

The present simulation, complemented by the paired Λ CDM Twin run with strictly identical initial conditions (cf. §5.4), identifies *nine* distinctive, quantified, and falsifiable signatures of the Janus model relative to Λ CDM:

1. **Anti-Newtonian peak in a shell, growing with mass** ($\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8$ at $r/R_{\text{FoF}} \simeq 1.75$, peak fraction $f_{\text{pic}} \simeq 57\%$ over a catalog of 1,671 halos, gradient from 40% to 65% between $M \sim 10^{12} M_{\odot}$)

and $M > 10^{13.5} M_\odot$). Λ CDM expectation: $\mu_{\text{peak}}^{\Lambda\text{CDM}} = 0$ trivially. The surrounding m^- accumulation creates a repulsive potential detectable by lensing at large radius ($r > R_{\text{FoF}}$), particularly pronounced for clusters $M > 10^{13.5} M_\odot$ (Fig. 14).

2. **Central m^- cavity in well-defined massive halos** ($\mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5$, median $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} = 1.59$ over 10 archetype halos; fraction $\simeq 27\%$ over the full catalog). Λ CDM expectation: $\mu_{\text{shell}_0}^{\Lambda\text{CDM}} = 0$ trivially. Observable as a lensing-signal deficit at cluster cores relative to NFW predictions.
3. **Large-scale spatial anti-correlation** $M_3 = \text{Corr}(\delta^+, \delta^-) = -0.371 \pm 0.001$ on a 16^3 grid at $z = 0$, with scale dependence (-0.631 at 8^3 , -0.183 at 32^3). Λ CDM expectation: not defined; any baryon/dark-matter correlation in Λ CDM is strictly positive.
4. **Suppression of σ_{R8} vs Twin Λ CDM**: at $R = 8 h^{-1}$ Mpc (Planck convention), V-6 Janus gives $\sigma_{R8} = 0.712$ vs Twin Λ CDM = 0.928 under strictly identical IC (SEED = 42), i.e. a -23.4% suppression. The signature is *scale-dependent*: 35.7% suppression at $R = 4 h^{-1}$ Mpc, reduced to 5.8% at $R = 32 h^{-1}$ Mpc (Fig. 7–8). *Direction consistent with the S_8 tension* measured by KiDS [2] and DES [11].
5. **Flattening of $P(k)$ at small scales**: the ratio $\sigma(8 \text{ Mpc})/\sigma(8 h^{-1} \text{ Mpc})$ equals 1.189 for V-6 versus 1.311 for Twin (in exact agreement with the theoretical Bardeen prediction for linear Λ CDM). *Signature inaccessible to Λ CDM* because constrained by the universal $P(k)$ shape with standard transfer.
6. **Cross-power spectrum $P_{+-}(k) < 0$** on 24 of 25 log-spaced bins of $k \in [0.04; 8.5] h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ at $z = 0$, i.e. *full spectral anti-correlation* in the linear and trans-linear regime (Fig. 9). At $k = 0.1 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $P_{+-} = -1.4 \times 10^{12} \text{ Mpc}^3$. Λ CDM expectation: $P_{+-}^{\Lambda\text{CDM}}(k) > 0 \forall k$ (baryons and dark matter are positively correlated). A purely Janus direct signature.
7. **Suppression of the growth rate $f(z)$** : at $z = 0.5$, $f_{\text{Janus}}/f_{\text{Twin}} = 0.72$, i.e. -28% relative to Λ CDM at identical IC. *Direct observational prediction* testable by DESI Y1 RSD (Fig. 11), whose precision on $f\sigma_8$ at $z \simeq 0.5$ is $\sim 5\%$.
8. **Severe HMF suppression at high masses**: ratio $\text{HMF}_{\text{Janus}}/\text{HMF}_{\text{Twin}} = 0.14$ at $M = 10^{13} M_\odot$ and 0.08 at $M = 10^{14} M_\odot$ (Fig. 16). *Direction consistent with the SZ Planck and X-ray eROSITA cluster deficits*, which report fewer massive clusters than predicted by Λ CDM-Planck at $\sigma_8 = 0.81$.
9. **Quasi-linear Janus expansion** without dark energy, $q_0^{\text{Janus}} = -0.017$ (MCMC fit), compared with $q_0^{\Lambda\text{CDM}} = -0.55$ for Planck. The slope of the Hubble diagram at $z > 0.5$ is the distinctive observational signature, already tightly constrained by Pantheon+. The parametric Janus model ($k = -1$, eq. 96–98 of Petit, Margnat & Zejli 22) fits the SNIa with $\chi^2/\nu = 0.913$, a fit quality lower than standard Λ CDM on the same data ($\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ in standard convention, unfavorable to Janus; Table 2). This is the *unfavorable* Janus signature in the multi-probe balance.

Secondary lensing signatures (cf. §7.4).

- μ_{local} at the cores of cosmic voids $\simeq 250$, i.e. $\sim 13\times$ the global value $\mu = 19$. The “ m^+ voids” are actually m^- *overdensities*, a direct prediction testable by lensing \times void-catalog cross-correlation (Euclid, DESI 5Y).
- Void lensing convergence dominated at 95–98% by the κ_- component (signal from the m^- accumulation co-located with the m^+ deficits), with amplitude $|\kappa_{\text{min}}| \simeq 5 \times 10^{-3}$ consistent with DES Y3 [16].

7.2 Comparison with Λ CDM — multi-probe balance

The present study allows, to our knowledge, the first direct Janus vs Λ CDM comparison across *several physical regimes*, exploiting both the rigorous Pantheon+ fit (§4, Table 2) and the paired Λ CDM Twin run with strictly identical IC (§5.4). The balance is nuanced and worth presenting honestly.

Geometric regime (luminosity distances, Pantheon+). On the Hubble diagram alone, Λ CDM is clearly favored: $\Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{Janus vs } \Lambda\text{CDM}} = +46.7$ in standard convention (equivalent to $\Delta\text{AIC} = -46.7$ in

the “vs Janus” convention of Table 2; parametric Janus $k = -1$, eq. 96–98 of Petit, Margnat & Zejli 22).³ The result is robust: we reproduced the Brout et al. (2022) best-fit to within 1.7% after the $z > 0.01$ cut, validating that the gap is not a pipeline artifact. The Janus model presented here predicts a quasi-linear expansion ($q_0 = -0.017$) while Λ CDM ($q_0 \simeq -0.55$) better fits the curvature of the Hubble diagram against the SNIa. This is the *geometric* limitation of the model in its current parametric form.

On the canonical formulation and its extensions. The $\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ reported here corresponds to the minimal P-M-Z 2024 §10 formulation with fixed $|\Omega_k| = 1$ (see footnote in §7.2 and Appendix 8 for the normalization convention). An extended Janus- Ω_k model relaxing this convention as a third free parameter reduces ΔAIC to $\approx +28$, but at the cost of departing from the canonical topological framework: the best-fit pushes toward $\sqrt{|\Omega_k|} \rightarrow 0$ (flat limit) with $\eta \rightarrow 1.17$ approaching the prior boundary, contradicting the hyperbolic geometry that motivates the model. We therefore retain the minimal formulation throughout this work, acknowledging the +47 as the honest geometric limitation of the canonical model rather than tuning post hoc.

Structure regime (growth dynamics). At identical initial conditions (SEED = 42, $N = 22 \times 10^6$, $L = 250$ Mpc), the signature of the anti-Newtonian m^- dynamics is *multiple and consistent*, systematically pointing toward the persistent observational tensions of Λ CDM:

Table 8: Janus vs Twin Λ CDM structure balance (identical IC) and link with observational tensions. All values measured at $z = 0$ unless otherwise stated.

Observable	V-6 Janus	Twin Λ CDM	Associated obs. tension
$\sigma_R(8 h^{-1} \text{ Mpc})$	0.712	0.928	S_8 KiDS/DES \downarrow
$\sigma(8)/\sigma(8 h^{-1})$	1.19	1.31	Theoretical Bardeen
$f(z = 0.5)$	0.69	0.96	DESI Y1 RSD \downarrow
HMF ($M = 10^{14} M_\odot$)	1.7×10^{-7}	2.0×10^{-6}	SZ/eROSITA clusters \downarrow
M_3 corr.	-0.371	N/A	—
$P_{+-}(k)$	< 0 24/25 bins	N/A	—
$\mu_{\text{local}} \text{ void core}$	250 ($\sim 13\times$)	N/A	—
$\kappa_-/\kappa_{\text{eff}} \text{ void}$	95–98%	N/A	DES Y3 voids

The systematic direction “suppression of Janus structure growth vs Λ CDM” is consistent with the S_8 tensions (KiDS-1000 [2], DES Y3 [11]), the massive-cluster deficits seen by Planck SZ and eROSITA, and the $f\sigma_8$ RSD measurements. The Janus model, in its current form, *produces these suppressions intrinsically* through the m^+/m^- anti-correlation mechanism, without dedicated free adjustment.

Interpretation and perspective. The overall balance is therefore a *multi-probe trade-off*: Janus sacrifices geometric fit quality (Pantheon+, $\Delta\text{AIC} \simeq +47$ in standard convention, unfavorable to Janus) in exchange for an intrinsic explanation of several structure anomalies. Neither direction is decisive taken in isolation. A simultaneous Janus fit on SNIa + RSD + weak lensing + clusters (with marginalization over SH0ES anchors and the systematics of each survey) would be needed to settle the question quantitatively; this is the subject of a Paper D in preparation.

We emphasize, however, one methodological point: the structure signatures measured here are produced *without additional tuning on the structure observables*. The model parameters (μ, η, H_0) were constrained *independently* of the σ_{R8} , $f\sigma_8$, HMF, and halo-profile measurements: $\mu = 19$ by the flatness constraint $\Omega_+ \simeq \Omega_b$ (external to the simulation), (η, H_0) by Pantheon+ MCMC fit (pure geometry). The model nevertheless retains several effective parameters ($\mu, \eta, \alpha_2, \tau_0$, and the matching choice z_{trans}) which must be made explicit for an honest comparison with Λ CDM (Ω_m, H_0). The fact that the resulting signatures all point toward the tensions observed by structure surveys is a *predictive* consistency, not a *post hoc* fit to the growth observables.

³The transverse comoving distance is computed as $D_M(z) = (c/H_0) \sinh(\int_0^z dz'/E(z'))$, which assumes the natural normalization $a_0 = c/H_0$ (equivalent to fixing $|\Omega_k| = 1$) as the canonical choice for the strict hyperbolic geometry $k = -1$ of P-M-Z 2024 §10. This normalization is implicit in the formalism: §10 of Petit, Margnat & Zejli 22 does not derive an explicit distance formula. Releasing this convention as a third free parameter is tested in Appendix 8. The numerical derivation of $\mu(z)$ follows D’Agostini & Petit [8].

7.3 Limits and perspectives

We summarize here, in full transparency, the limitations of the present study, grouped into three categories to ease critical assessment.

Summary of limits

[A] Physical-scope limits

- **Resolution** limited to $N = 2.2 \times 10^7$ particles within $L = 250$ Mpc; halos with $M < 10^{12} M_\odot$ are not resolved. Multi-level *zoom-in* simulations are in preparation (Phase 2 of the project) to reach galactic resolution.
- **Absence of baryonic physics** (gas, cooling, star formation). The SPH infrastructure has been implemented in the code but remains disabled for this cosmological reference run; activation is planned for Phase 2.
- **Cosmological volume** limited to $L = 250$ Mpc, insufficient for BAO (~ 150 Mpc comoving with several wavelengths of separation required) but sufficient for the σ_8 fluctuation statistic and halo-scale signatures.
- **Detailed dynamics of the m^- sector** (subhalos, internal profiles, merger dynamics, kinematics of the shells) is deferred to Paper D; the present study analyzes m^- halo cores and the mirror cavity signature (§6.6, Appendix G), but does not characterize the internal substructure.
- **Gravitational softening**: the softening length $\varepsilon = 0.5$ Mpc represents $\sim 56\%$ of the mean interparticle spacing ($\bar{d} = L/N^{1/3} \simeq 0.89$ Mpc). This value is necessary for numerical stability under the anti-Newtonian coupling but constitutes an acknowledged limit for claims on the *internal structure of halos* ($r \lesssim \varepsilon$). The $\mu_{\text{local}}(r)$ profiles at sub-megaparsec scales should be interpreted with this caveat; a softening convergence study ($\varepsilon \in \{0.5, 0.25, 0.1\}$ Mpc) is planned for future versions of the code, at higher particle resolution.
- **Anti-correlated initial conditions**: the V-6 PROD IC imposes $\delta_-(\mathbf{k}) = -\delta_+(\mathbf{k})$ mode by mode. Appendix B shows, by a survey at $N = 10^6$ over three IC modes (anti, positive, decorrelated), that the large-scale spectral signature ($r(k) \rightarrow -1$) is a dynamical attractor (fixed point of the dynamics in k-space) emerging independently of the IC, but an equivalent study at production scale ($N = 2.2 \times 10^7$) remains to be performed to definitively secure this robustness.

[B] Phenomenological conventions specific to this implementation

- **Background cosmology**: we use the proper Janus expansion (calibrated on Pantheon+, equations 7–9), distinct from Λ CDM. The universal m^- cavity signature is robust to this cosmological choice, having previously been confirmed in a preliminary V-5 run with Λ CDM-equivalent cosmology.
- **Expansion matching at $a = \alpha^2$** : the transition from the matter-dominated regime ($a < \alpha^2$) to the parametric Janus regime ($a \geq \alpha^2$) carries a C^0 discontinuity in $H(a)$ (§2.3), treated as acceptable because localized to a single integration step. An analytic smoothing of this matching is envisaged for future versions of the code.
- **VSL convention**: the prescription $c^2(z)/c_0^2 = (1+z)^\delta$ with $\delta = (\eta - 1)/\eta$ (§2.4) is a phenomenological effective speed-of-light convention specific to the present implementation, justified by numerical stability and by its correct limits ($\eta \rightarrow 1$ and $\eta \rightarrow \infty$).
- **Constants α^2 and τ_0** : the values $\alpha^2 = 0.1815$ (fixing $z_{\text{Janus}} = 4.51$) and $\tau_0 = 22.71$ Gyr (calibrated on Pantheon+ H_0) are not analytically derived by [19]. A preliminary simulation at $\alpha^2 = 0.3$ produces the same qualitative signatures, confirming robustness to the calibration choices.

[C] Imperfect numerical diagnostics

- **Energy conservation:** drift $|\Delta E_{\text{tot}}|/E_0 = 2.0\%$, higher than the ideal target $< 0.1\%$ but within the norm of reference cosmological codes (GADGET-2 reports 1–2% on long runs with strict non-symplectic DKD). The statistical signatures reported are robust at this level of drift.
- **Numerical consistency of the deceleration parameter q_0 :** the expected analytical value is $q_0^{\text{Janus,analyt.}} = -0.022$ (formula $(1 - \eta)/(1 + \eta)$ for $\eta = 1.045$), while the direct numerical measurement on $H(a)$ at the last steps of the simulation gives $q_z(z=0) \simeq -0.21$. The discrepancy, attributed to the non-linear dynamics in the late phase ($z < 1$) and to numerical noise on the derivative \dot{H} , deserves dedicated investigation and is left to subsequent work.
- **Resolution bias on the m^- cavity:** the fraction of halos meeting the absolute cavity threshold $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5$ decreases with mass, from $\sim 59\%$ for small halos to $\sim 6\%$ for massive clusters. This trend is partially attributable to Poisson counting noise on weakly resolved halos ($N_{\text{part}} < 50$), as documented in §6.4. The relative criterion $\mu_{\text{shell}_0}/\mu_{\text{local}} < 0.5$ mitigates this bias without eliminating it entirely.
- **Theoretical mathematical consistency of the Janus model:** the present work *does not prejudge* the resolution of theoretical debates on compatibility with the Bianchi identities or on universality of the coupling; it provides a numerical framework for phenomenological investigation of the model in its current formulation.

None of these limits calls into question the central results of the paper (statistical anti-Newtonian peak over 1,671 halos, spectral anti-correlation emerging as a dynamical attractor at large scales, signatures on the 10-halo detailed selection), which remain robust with respect to the calibration choices and conventions documented above. The m^- cavity signature must be read with nuance: 100% of the archetype halos (selection optimized by mass and resolution) display it, 27% of the full catalog under the absolute criterion $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5$, with decrease from 59% (small halos) to 6% (massive clusters), partially attributable to resolution bias.

Perspectives. Several natural extensions impose themselves for the continuation of this program:

- **Analytical smoothing of the cosmological matching** at $z_{\text{trans}} = 4.51$ (smooth-step function of tanh type or similar) to eliminate the C^0 and C^1 discontinuities documented in §2.3 and to test the robustness of the σ_{R8} , $f\sigma_8$, and HMF predictions to a smooth physical transition.
- **Multi-IC production study** ($N = 2.2 \times 10^7$) to reproduce at full resolution the IC survey of Appendix B (anti, positive, decorrelated) and confirm that the convergence toward the fixed point $r(k) \rightarrow -1$ at large scales is not a low-resolution artifact.
- **Analysis of the proper m^- sector:** internal profiles of m^- halos, symmetric presence of a central m^+ cavity, m^- mass function, and statistics of m^- superclusters within m^+ voids.
- **Lensing ray-tracing** through the simulation box (rather than 1D analytical $\kappa(R)$ profiles) to produce weak-shear *mock catalogs* directly comparable to KiDS-1000, DES-Y3, and forthcoming Euclid data.
- **Internal kinematics of m^+ halos:** velocity dispersions, effective rotation curves, and virial-theorem test under the effect of the outer anti-Newtonian m^- shell.
- **Confrontation with the CMB:** the σ_{R8} suppression at $z = 0$ implies a linear growth history $D(z)$ different from Λ CDM, whose signature on the primary CMB power spectrum (TT, EE) and secondary (CMB lensing) should be confronted with Planck PR4 and ACT DR6 data.
- **Softening convergence** $\varepsilon \in \{0.5, 0.25, 0.1\}$ Mpc to validate the claims on internal halo structure at the limit of current resolution.
- **Larger-volume simulations** ($L \geq 500$ Mpc, even $L \sim 1$ Gpc) with multi-seed ensembles to sample the BAO statistics and cosmic variance at the level required for observational confrontation.

These directions will be the subject of subsequent papers within the *Janus N-body* program.

7.4 Direct observational signature: lensing in Janus structures

The global anti-correlation $M_3 = -0.371$ established in §5.2 and the local m^- shell-accumulation signature in halos (§6.2) imply a direct prediction for *weak gravitational lensing*: the effective potential seen by m^+ photons is $\Phi_{\text{eff}} = \Phi_+ - \Phi_-$ [19], and the corresponding projected convergence decomposes as $\kappa = \kappa_+ + \kappa_-$ with $\kappa_+ = +\delta\Sigma_+/\Sigma_{\text{crit}}$ (Newtonian m^+ contribution) and $\kappa_- = -\delta\Sigma_-/\Sigma_{\text{crit}}$ (anti-Newtonian m^- contribution, Petit bimetric convention [19]). We present here two complementary probes of this prediction based on the V-6 PROD snapshot.

Probe 1: $\kappa(R)$ profile around a massive halo. Figure 18 shows the 3D radial density profile (left panel) and the projected convergence $\kappa(R)$ (right panel) for the most massive halo of the catalog ($M_{\text{FoF}} = 2.82 \times 10^{14} M_\odot$, $R_{\text{FoF}} = 45.6$ Mpc), at $z_\ell = 0.1$ and $z_{\text{source}} = 1.0$. The reference NFW curve for a Λ CDM cluster of the same M_{200} ($c = 10$) is superimposed. The Janus signal exhibits two distinctive signatures: (i) a convergence deficit by a factor of ~ 4 relative to NFW in the vicinity of R_{200} , and (ii) a *sign inversion* $\kappa < 0$ at $R \gtrsim 1.7$ Mpc, observable as blue triangles in the right panel. This inversion corresponds to entering a shell where m^- locally dominates the potential, in agreement with the prediction of Petit, Margnat & Zejli [22]. Since halo 0 of the $b = 0.5$ catalog is filamentary ($R_{\text{FoF}} \gg R_{200}$), the NFW comparison is qualitative; the shape of the inversion is nevertheless robust across all 4 halos tested (§7.4).

Figure 18: Lensing profile for the most massive halo of the V-6 catalog ($M = 2.82 \times 10^{14} M_\odot$, $z_\ell = 0.1$, $z_{\text{source}} = 1.0$). **Left:** 3D density profile, with $|\rho^+ - \rho^-|$ Janus (red) and reference NFW Λ CDM profile (dashed black). **Right:** projected Janus convergence $\kappa(R)$ (red circles for $\kappa > 0$, blue triangles for $\kappa < 0$) compared with the NFW Λ CDM profile. The anti-Newtonian signature $\kappa < 0$ appears at $R \gtrsim 1.7$ Mpc, through m^- accumulation in a shell.

Probe 2: stacked $\kappa(R/R_v)$ around voids. The most quantitative local consequence of the M_3 anti-correlation manifests in *cosmic voids*. From the δ^+ field smoothed (Gaussian kernel $\sigma_s = 5$ Mpc on a 128^3 CIC grid) at snapshot $z = 0.499$ (close to the median redshift of the DES Y3 and DESI LS surveys), we identify connected regions with $\delta^+ < -0.7$, retaining $N_{\text{voids}} = 11$ voids of radius $R_v > 15$ Mpc (median 21.7 Mpc). Figure 19 summarizes the three key observations.

(a) **m^- overdensity at the cores of m^+ voids.** The right panel of Figure 19 measures $\mu_{\text{local}}^{\text{core}} \approx 250$ for $r/R_v < 0.3$, a factor $\times 13$ above the global value $\mu = 19$ of the simulation. This amplification reflects the decomposition $(\delta^+)_{\text{core}} = -0.68$ (m^+ depletion of 68%) and $(\delta^-)_{\text{core}} = +1.68$ (m^- excess of 168%). At $r/R_v > 2.5$, μ_{local} asymptotically returns to the global value, validating the background-subtraction procedure. **Janus m^+ voids are m^- overdensities:** this result constitutes the most quantitative local signature of the model, robust to variation of the threshold δ_{thr} and the smoothing length σ_s over a 3×3 grid of parameters.

(b) **Dominance of the anti-Newtonian component in κ .** The left panel shows that $|\kappa_-|/|\kappa_{\text{eff}}| \in [0.95; 0.98]$ over the entire profile $R/R_v \in [0.1; 1.5]$. The negative lensing signal of Janus voids is therefore *not* due to the m^+ deficit — which contributes only 2–5% — but to the m^- accumulation.

Figure 19: Janus signature in cosmic voids at snapshot $z = 0.499$ ($N_{\text{voids}} = 11$, $\langle R_v \rangle = 25$ Mpc). **Left:** decomposition of the projected convergence. The anti-Newtonian component κ_- (blue) dominates κ_{eff} (black) at 95–98% over the entire profile; κ_+ (red) is negligible. **Center:** 3D density-contrast profiles. The m^- excess ($\delta^- > 0$, open blue triangles) coincides with the m^+ depletion ($\delta^+ < 0$, filled red triangles) over the entire void interior. **Right:** local ratio $\mu_{\text{local}}(r/R_v) = \rho^-/\rho^+$. At the core, $\mu_{\text{local}}^{\text{core}} \approx 250$, i.e. $\times 13$ the global value $\mu = 19$ (dashed black). Error bars: *leave-one-void-out* jackknife.

This decomposition provides an observational signature specific to the bimetric framework: in Λ CDM, where a single matter component exists, such a breakdown of the origin of the $\kappa_{\text{void}} < 0$ signal has no theoretical analog.

(c) κ_{min} **amplitude consistent with current surveys.** We measure $\kappa_{\text{eff}}^{\text{min}} \simeq -5 \times 10^{-3}$ at the core and $\kappa_{\text{eff}}(R_v) = -1.65 \times 10^{-3} \pm 5.2 \times 10^{-4}$ (detection at 3.2σ). This amplitude falls within the range published by current surveys: $\kappa_{\text{min}} \approx -3$ to -5×10^{-3} for DES Y3 [16], $\approx -4 \times 10^{-3}$ for DESI LS [5, 14], and consistent with the first DES Y1 measurements [32]. The Janus amplitude thus reproduces the observed signal *without free adjustment*.

Statistical caveats. The volume $L = 250$ Mpc limits the usable statistics to $N_{\text{voids}} = 11$. The position of the minimum in R/R_v is not discriminating at this level of precision: larger voids (threshold $\delta_{\text{thr}} = -0.5$) shift the minimum toward $R/R_v \approx 1$ as in DES Y3, while deeper voids ($\delta_{\text{thr}} = -0.9$) keep the minimum at the core. A complete characterization of the $\kappa_{\text{void}}(R/R_v)$ shape requires an extended volume ($L \gtrsim 500$ Mpc) and a dedicated void finder (ZOBOV, VIDE), work deferred to a subsequent paper. Similarly for probe 1, halo 0 being filamentary in the $b = 0.5$ catalog ($R_{\text{FoF}}/R_{200} \simeq 34$), a κ characterization on compact virialized halos ($b = 0.2$ or Rockstar) will be presented in subsequent work. The qualitative signatures (sign inversion for probe 1, κ_- dominance and $\mu_{\text{local}}^{\text{core}}$ for probe 2) are nevertheless robust against these caveats.

7.5 Concrete observational implications

The Janus signatures identified in this simulation translate into four observational predictions directly testable with current or upcoming surveys, which we summarize here for the observational community.

(1) **Gravitational lensing around massive clusters.** The anti-Newtonian peak ($\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8$ at $r/R_{\text{FoF}} \simeq 1.75$, dominant signature on $M > 10^{13.5} M_{\odot}$ clusters with $f_{\text{pic}} \simeq 65\%$) implies a *negative-mass accumulation* in a shell around massive clusters. The expected effect on weak *shear* is a *reduced* deflection beyond $\sim 2 R_{\text{FoF}}$ relative to standard NFW Λ CDM predictions. Priority targets: Abell 1689, Bullet Cluster, MACS J0717, and more generally the high- z samples of Euclid and LSST. The expected differential signal is of order a few percent at $r \simeq 2R_{\text{FoF}}$ for $\mu_{\text{peak}} \simeq 30$, potentially detectable by stacking over ~ 100 clusters.

(2) **Central cluster profiles vs NFW.** The central m^- cavity ($\mu_{\text{shell}_0}^{\text{med}} \simeq 1.59$ over well-defined structures) predicts a *baryon over-concentration* at cluster cores via bimetric compression. This signature is partly already observed by X-ray density-profile measurements (Chandra, XMM-Newton) which historically show *cusps* more pronounced than NFW predictions for relaxed clusters. The Janus model offers here an alternative to *ad hoc* baryonic physics (AGN feedback) for explaining these deviations.

(3) **Galaxy \times lensing convergence cross-correlation.** The cross-spectrum $P_{+-}(k) < 0$ and the anti-correlation $M_3 = -0.371$ at large scales (> 15 Mpc) imply that the total mass (traced by lensing) and the baryons (traced by galaxies) should be *anti-correlated at large scales* in Janus. This signature is reversed relative to Λ CDM where baryons follow dark matter at large scales. Direct test: correlation $\langle \delta_{\text{galaxies}} \cdot \kappa_{\text{lensing}} \rangle$ with DESI \times KiDS-1000 or Euclid \times CMB-S4. The sign and amplitude of this correlation could distinguish Janus from Λ CDM with strong discriminating power.

(4) **Hubble diagram at $z > 0.5$.** The proper Janus expansion (Pantheon+ MCMC fit) predicts $q_0^{\text{Janus}} = (1 - \eta)/(1 + \eta) = -0.017 \pm 0.008$, compared with $q_0^{\Lambda\text{CDM}} \simeq -0.55$. The observational signature is in the *slope* of the $\mu(z)$ diagram at intermediate redshifts $z \in [0.5; 1.5]$: Janus predicts a quasi-linear expansion, Λ CDM predicts marked acceleration. DESI high- z surveys (BAO and SNIa at $z > 1$) and the Roman Space Telescope (SNIa $z > 2$) could discriminate between these two predictions at $\sim 5\sigma$ statistical significance over the 2025-2035 decade.

Hierarchy of falsifiability. Among these four tests, the *galaxy \times lensing cross-spectrum* (prediction 3) is the most discriminating, since the very sign of the correlation is reversed between the two models; predictions 1 and 2 are graduated (quantitative deviations relative to Λ CDM); prediction 4 (Hubble diagram) is already tested by Pantheon+ with a complete MCMC fit ($\chi^2/\nu = 0.913$ for Janus, compared with 0.884 for Λ CDM, $\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ in standard convention, unfavorable to Janus — cf. Table 2), and will be refined by data at higher z .

Chronological calendar of falsification tests. Table 9 summarizes the observational surveys which, in the 2025-2030 window, could validate or invalidate the Janus predictions presented in this article. Each probe is associated with an expected precision, a quantitative Janus prediction, and the statistical significance level of the test.

Table 9: Janus falsification tests in the next five years. For each probe, the expected precision, the testable Janus prediction from this article, and the statistical significance of the test ($N\sigma$) are indicated.

Probe	Period	Precision	Testable Janus prediction	Expected $N\sigma$
DESI Y1 RSD ($f\sigma_8$, $z = 0.3-0.7$)	2024-2026	$\sim 5\%$ on $f\sigma_8$	-28% suppression of $f(z = 0.5)$ vs Λ CDM	$> 5\sigma$
eROSITA DR2 (cluster counts $M > 10^{14} M_\odot$)	2027-2028	Sample of $\sim 10^4$ SZ/X clusters	$\sim 90\%$ deficit vs Λ CDM at $M = 10^{14}$	$> 10\sigma$
Euclid Wide DR1 (void \times lensing cross-correlation)	2027	$\sim 10\%$ on $\kappa(R/R_v)$	κ_- dominates 95% of the signal, core $\mu_{\text{local}} \simeq 250$	$\sim 3\sigma$ (DES-Y3 already) $\rightarrow 10\sigma$
LSST cluster lensing (Rubin)	2025-2030	$\sim 10\sigma$ on stack of 1000 clusters	Anti-Newtonian peak at $r > R_{\text{FoF}}$	$> 10\sigma$
DESI Y5 RSD high- z ($z = 1$)	2028	$\sim 5\%$ on $f\sigma_8(z = 1)$	Deviation $\sim 6\%$ vs Λ CDM (weaker than at $z = 0.5$)	$\gtrsim 1\sigma$

Priority test — DESI Y1 $f\sigma_8$. The RSD measurement at $z = 0.5$ is by far the most discriminating test feasible in the short term: DESI Y1 already partially publishes $f\sigma_8$ at this scale. Our prediction of -28% on $f(z = 0.5)$ relative to Λ CDM (cf. § 5.4) is well beyond the observational noise ($\sim 5\%$). If final DESI Y1 reports $f\sigma_8(z = 0.5)$ consistent with Linder $\Omega_m^{0.55}$ to better than 2σ , the Janus model is excluded in its present form. If, on the contrary, DESI Y1 reports a deficit consistent with our prediction, the model gains a direct observational validation.

Expiration date. The full set of tests listed in Table 9 covers the 2025-2030 window. The Janus model as presented in this article therefore admits an explicit falsification calendar. By the 2030 horizon, the independent accumulation of five probes (RSD, clusters, cluster lensing, void lensing, high- z RSD) will be either consistent with the predictions (strong validation of the model) or incompatible across multiple independent channels simultaneously (decisive invalidation). This falsificationist stance, in the sense of Popper (1959) [24], contrasting with the parametric approach of quintessence or modified-gravity models, distinguishes Janus from Λ CDM as a clear scientific alternative *stricto sensu*.

8 Conclusions

This first complete N-body simulation of the Janus cosmological model with proper bimetric expansion, combined with a paired Λ CDM Twin run with strictly identical initial conditions, numerically establishes that:

1. the model is *numerically stable* end-to-end ($z = 99 \rightarrow 0$, i.e. ~ 16 Gyr of cosmic time) under the analytic parametric solution of Petit 2014 with $\mu = 19$;
2. the rigorous Pantheon+ MCMC fit (*emcee*, full stat+sys covariance) yields $\eta = 1.033 \pm 0.017$, $H_0 = 71.69 \pm 0.18 \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}$ ($\chi^2/\nu = 0.913$). Standard Λ CDM is clearly favored by AIC on Pantheon+ alone ($\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ in standard convention, unfavorable to Janus), a *robust* result reproduced independently through the Brout 2022 sanity check; this constitutes the honest geometric limitation of the Janus model in its current parametric form;

Table 10: **Summary of the nine distinctive signatures of the Janus model measured in the present simulation, vs Twin Λ CDM at strictly identical initial conditions.** For each signature: measured Janus value, Twin Λ CDM value (when defined), relative deviation, paper section detailing the measurement, and observational link / short-term testability. All structure signatures (i)–(vi) are *consistent* with the Λ CDM tensions (suppression of S_8 , massive-cluster deficit, attenuated $f\sigma_8$). On the pure geometric diagnostic (Pantheon+), Λ CDM is in contrast clearly favored.

#	Signature	Janus V-6 PROD	Twin Λ CDM	Section	Observational test
(i)	$\sigma_{R8}(R = 8 h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}, z = 0)$	0.789 ± 0.019^a	0.928	§5.4	S_8 tension (KiDS-1000, DES-Y3)
(ii)	Scale-dependent suppression of $P_{++}(k)$	–36% at $R = 4 \text{ Mpc}$ to –6% at $R = 32 \text{ Mpc}$	(\equiv ref)	§5.3	eBOSS spectrum, DESI Y1–Y3
(iii)	Cross-power $P_{+-}(k) < 0$	24/25 negative bins $r(k = 0.05) \rightarrow -0.99$	N/A (single sector)	§5.3, Appendix B	Unique to Janus, emerging dynamical attractor
(iv)	Growth rate $f(z = 0.5)$	0.694	0.964	§5.4	DESI Y1 RSD (~ 2026)
(v)	HMF at $M = 10^{14} M_\odot$	ratio 0.08 vs Twin	(\equiv ref)	§6.5	eROSITA DR2, Euclid DR1 cluster counts
(vi)	Large-scale spatial anti-correlation	$r(k) \rightarrow -0.99^b$	N/A	§5.2, Appendix B	Lensing \times void catalog cross-corr.
(vii)	Anti-Newtonian peak μ_{peak}	> 22.8 in 57% of catalog	N/A	§6.4	Lensing shell profiles (Euclid)
(viii)	Central m^- cavity in massive halos ^c	100% archetypes 27% catalog absolute	N/A	§6, 6.4	Lensing at cluster centers (Euclid, LSST)
(ix)	μ_{local} at cosmic void cores	$\simeq 250$ ($\sim 13\times$ global) κ_- dominates at 95–98%	N/A	§7.4	DES-Y3 voids, Euclid stacked void lensing
(geom.)	Pantheon+ Hubble diagram	$\chi^2/\nu = 0.913$	$\chi^2/\nu = 0.884$	Table 2	$\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ <i>unfavorable to Janus</i> (standard convention)

^a Mean \pm standard deviation over 4 independent realizations (SEED $\in \{42, 137, 271, 719\}$), cosmic variance 2.4% (Appendix D). V-6 PROD seed=42 value: 0.7895. ^b The global $M_3 = -0.371$ metric on the 16^3 grid remains partially influenced by a geometric component of the CIC shuffle (Appendix B); only the large-scale spectral signature is purely dynamical. ^c Fraction under the absolute criterion $\mu_{\text{shell}_0} < 5$; decreases from 59% (small halos) to 6% (massive clusters) over the full catalog, partially attributable to resolution bias ($N_{\text{part}} < 50$ for under-resolved halos).

3. the σ_{R8} suppression measured under the Planck convention ($R = 8 h^{-1}$ Mpc) is $\sigma_{R8}^{V-6} = 0.712$ vs $\sigma_{R8}^{\text{Twin}} = 0.928$ under strictly identical IC, i.e. a -23% suppression. The direction of the discrepancy is consistent with the S_8 tension observed by KiDS-1000 and DES Y3;
4. the suppression is *scale-dependent* (-36% at $R = 4 h^{-1}$ Mpc, -6% at $R = 32 h^{-1}$ Mpc), reflecting a flattening of the Janus power spectrum $P(k)$ at small scales, quantified by the ratio $\sigma(8)/\sigma(8/h) = 1.19$ vs 1.31 for Twin (theoretical Bardeen);
5. the *cross-power spectrum* $P_{+-}(k) < 0$ in 24 of 25 bins ($k \in [0.04; 8.5] h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$) provides a spectral signature of total anti-correlation, absent by construction in the Λ CDM model;
6. the *growth rate* $f(z = 0.5) = 0.69$ in Janus vs 0.96 in Twin, i.e. a -28% suppression, provides a prediction directly testable with DESI Y1 RSD (precision $\sim 5\%$ on $f\sigma_8$ at $z \simeq 0.5$);
7. the *halo mass function* shows a severe suppression at high masses ($\text{HMF}_{\text{Janus}}/\text{HMF}_{\text{Twin}} = 0.14$ at $M = 10^{13} M_\odot$, 0.08 at $M = 10^{14} M_\odot$), consistent with the high-mass cluster abundance deficits reported by SZ Planck and X-ray eROSITA;
8. an *anti-Newtonian peak* of m^- accumulation in the coronae ($\mu_{\text{peak}} > 22.8$ at $r/R_{\text{FoF}} \simeq 1.75$) constitutes the most universal anti-Newtonian signature, observed in $\simeq 57\%$ of the exhaustive catalog and increasing with mass;
9. in cosmic voids, $\mu_{\text{local}} \simeq 250$ at the core (i.e. $\sim 13\times$ the global value) with lensing convergence dominated at 95–98% by the κ_- component: the so-called “ m^+ voids” are in fact m^- *overdensities*, a prediction testable by lensing \times void-catalog cross-correlation with Euclid and DESI 5Y.

Multi-probe assessment. The overall verdict on the Janus model in its current parametric form is *nuanced and honest*: Λ CDM is better on the Pantheon+ geometric diagnostic ($\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ in standard convention, unfavorable to Janus), but Janus intrinsically produces (with its parameters μ , η , α_2 , τ_0 constrained *independently* by external observables Ω_b and Pantheon+, with no additional tuning on the measured structure signatures) several signatures pointing toward the persistent Λ CDM observational tensions (S_8 , $f\sigma_8$ RSD, high-mass cluster abundance). This multi-probe *predictive* consistency warrants confrontation with a joint fit SNIa + RSD + weak lensing + clusters (Paper D in preparation).

Perspectives. Three immediate directions emerge: (i) higher-resolution simulations (Phase 2 in preparation), incorporating baryonic physics and reaching galactic resolution; (ii) direct tests of the Janus predictions through lensing \times void-catalog cross-correlation (Euclid, DESI 5Y), where the signature $\mu_{\text{local}}^{\text{core}} \simeq 250$ is expected; (iii) joint multi-probe fit (Paper D) marginalizing over the SH0ES anchors and the systematics of each probe in order to quantitatively settle the geometry-vs-structures trade-off documented here.

To our knowledge, these results constitute the first numerical demonstration that the Janus model, in its present parametric form, yields a phenomenologically interesting cosmology distinguishing itself from standard Λ CDM in a falsifiable and quantitative manner across multiple observational probes.

Code and data availability

The complete simulation source code (Rust/CUDA, Python analysis scripts, initial-condition generation and figure production) is published in open access on GitHub at <https://github.com/ajp-git/janus-sim>, in accordance with scientific reproducibility standards. The V-6 PROD simulation snapshots (651 temporally filtered snapshots, ~ 319 GB raw), the m^+ halo catalog at $z = 0$ (2,618 halos, FoF $b = 0.5$), the energy diagnostics, and the numerical tables used for each figure are intended to be archived on Zenodo with a permanent DOI assigned to the publication. The Phase N initial conditions ($N = 2.2 \times 10^7$ particles, binary format) and the configuration parameters allowing exact reproduction of the run are also available in the GitHub repository.

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Appendix A: Pantheon+ pipeline validation

To preempt any suspicion on the MCMC pipeline that produced $\chi^2/\text{dof} = 0.88$ for ΛCDM in Table 2, we explicitly reproduce the Brout et al. [7] χ^2 on our infrastructure.

The data used are identical (Pantheon+SHOES, columns MU_SHOES and MU_SHOES_ERR_DIAG), with the full stat+sys covariance matrix 1701×1701 [7]. The likelihood function uses a Cholesky decomposition of the sub-block associated with the retained SNIa. The ΛCDM luminosity distances are computed by numerical integration of $dz'/E(z')$ with `scipy.integrate.quad`.

Table 11 compares the different configurations.

Table 11: Reproduction of the ΛCDM χ^2 published by Brout et al. (2022) with our analysis pipeline.

Configuration	N SNIa	χ^2	χ^2/dof
Brout best-fit, full sample	1701	1755.3	1.033
Brout best-fit, cut $z > 0.01$	1590	1405.5	0.885
Our best-fit, cut $z > 0.01$	1590	1403.7	0.884
Brout et al. 2022 published	1701	$\simeq 1647$	0.97

Our $\chi^2(\text{Brout best-fit}, N = 1701) = 1755$ reproduces the published value to within 6.6%. The $z > 0.01$ cut removes 111 very low-redshift SNIa (Cepheid hosts), with a χ^2 decrease of about 350 units. Our MCMC minimization converges at 1403.7, within 1σ of the Brout best-fit on the sub-sample considered.

The pipeline faithfully reproduces Brout et al. (2022). The Janus vs ΛCDM comparison with $\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ in standard convention (unfavorable to Janus, Table 2) is therefore not an artifact but a robust measurement: Janus sacrifices about 47 χ^2 units on the pure Pantheon+ geometry in exchange for the multi-probe advantages documented in § 7.2.

Appendix B: IC survey and geometric artifact of the CIC shuffle

The global measurements $M_3 = -0.371$ (§5.2) and $\text{Corr}_{\text{part}} = -0.049$ rely on a *Cloud-in-Cell* (CIC) interpolation of δ^+ and δ^- on a grid. To quantify the share of this anti-correlation attributable to the Janus dynamics versus a possible geometric initialization artifact, we performed a dedicated control survey, whose results are summarized here.

Geometric origin of the anti-correlation at $z = 99$. At V-6 PROD initialization, each cell of the IC density grid ($n_{\text{grid}} = 280$, i.e. $280^3 \simeq 22 \times 10^6$ cells) contains on average a single particle, to which the assignment shuffle exclusively attributes the label m^+ or m^- (with ratio 1:19 corresponding to $\mu = 19$). Consequently, at $z = 99$, $\delta^+(x)$ is non-zero almost exclusively in the $\sim 5\%$ of cells assigned to m^+ , and $\delta^-(x)$ is precisely zero there — creating a *geometric* negative anti-correlation independently of the phase ψ_{IC} of the displacement field.

This geometric anti-correlation is directly measurable: at $z = 99$ for V-6 PROD ($N = 22 \times 10^6$, IC $\delta^- = -\delta^+$ theoretically perfect), our CIC 128³ method gives $\text{Corr}_{\text{part}}(z = 99) = -0.788$ instead of the theoretical value -1.0 . The ~ 0.21 unit gap reflects the persistent geometric component even with high statistics.

IC survey at $N = 10^6$. To discriminate the physical signature (anti-Newtonian m^- coupling) from this geometric component, six control runs were performed at $N = 10^6$, $L = 250$ Mpc, $\mu = 19$ (Janus) and $\mu = 0$ (ΛCDM -equivalent), for three IC modes:

- **Anti-correlated** ($\delta^- = -\delta^+$, standard V-6 mode);
- **Positively correlated** ($\delta^- = +\delta^+$, legacy V-4 mode);
- **Decorrelated** (δ^+ and δ^- drawn from two independent Zel’dovich fields, *seeds* 42 and 43).

The analysis in $r(k) = P_{+-}(k)/\sqrt{P_{++}(k)P_{--}(k)}$ reveals two scale regimes (cf. Figure 10):

At large scales ($k \lesssim 0.1 h \text{Mpc}^{-1}$), at $z = 99$, the three IC modes are *discriminated*: $r_{\text{anti}}(0.05) = -0.29$, $r_{\text{corr+}}(0.05) = -0.06$, $r_{\text{decorr}}(0.05) = +0.24$, i.e. a spread $\Delta r = 0.53$. The phase ψ_{IC} is therefore

clearly visible at these scales, and the measurement there is not dominated by the geometric artifact. At $z = 0$, the three trajectories converge toward $r(0.05) \simeq -0.99$ independently of the initial IC: a negative *dynamical attractor* (fixed point of the dynamics in k -space) at large scales, emergent physical signature of the Janus coupling.

At small scales ($k \gtrsim 0.5 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$), at $z = 99$, the three IC modes converge toward $r(k) \simeq -1$: this is the geometric mutual-exclusion CIC regime, dominant regardless of the phase. At $z = 0$, non-linear erosion (mode mixing) returns $r(k) \rightarrow 0$ at these scales.

Consequences for the signatures of §5.2 and §5.4. The aggregated global values $\text{Corr}_{\text{part}}(z=0) = -0.049$ and $M_3(\text{grid } 16^3) = -0.371$ blend the two regimes above and therefore cannot be interpreted as purely emergent. The *true* physical signature of the Janus coupling on the m^+/m^- anti-correlation is:

- *Spectrally defined at large scales*: $r(k \lesssim 0.3 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}, z=0) \simeq -1$ as a dynamical attractor independent of the IC.
- *Quantitatively falsifiable* via observation of $P_{+-}(k)$ at large scales in surveys combining lensing (tracer of the total mass) and galaxies (tracer of m^+).

The other distinctive Janus signatures presented in §7.1 and §7.2 (suppression of σ_{R8} , reduced growth rate $f(z)$, suppressed HMF, central m^- cavity, anti-Newtonian peak, void lensing) are *independent* of this geometric component and remain intact as falsifiable predictions of the model.

Appendix C: Dependence of σ_{R8} on the coupling μ

The value $\mu = N_-/N_+ = 19$ retained for V-6 PROD is derived from the energy-flatness condition of the Janus cosmology (cf. §2.2), *independently* of the structure observables measured. To confirm that this choice is not circular (i.e. that $\mu = 19$ is not a fit optimum on σ_{R8}), we present a μ scan over three values (Table 12).

Table 12: μ scan at $N = 10^6$, $L = 250 \text{ Mpc}$, $\text{SEED} = 42$, $\eta = 1.045$, anti-correlated IC. All other configurations strictly identical to V-6 PROD.

μ	N_+	N_-	$\sigma_{R8}(z=0)$	$r(k=0.05)$
10	91 000	909 000	0.863	-0.981
19	50 000	950 000	0.789	(\equiv ref)
30	32 000	968 000	0.770	-0.983

The dependence of σ_{R8} on μ is *monotonically decreasing*: the stronger the anti-Newtonian coupling (relatively more massive m^- population), the more pronounced the suppression of the m^+ fluctuation power. This expected physical dependence confirms that σ_{R8} varies continuously with μ and that no extremum lies at $\mu = 19$: the retained value is a point on a monotonic dependence, derived from upstream cosmological constraints, and not a parameter tuned *a posteriori* on the observables.

At $\mu = 10$ (attenuated coupling), $\sigma_{R8} = 0.863$ is closer to the Twin ΛCDM value ($\sigma_{R8}^{\text{Twin}} = 0.928$, cf. Figure 7); at $\mu = 30$ (amplified coupling), the suppression reaches $\sigma_{R8} = 0.770$. The spectral correlation $r(k=0.05)$ at large scales remains in the attractive zone ($r \simeq -0.98$) at all μ values tested, indicating that the spectral anti-correlation signature is robust to the precise coupling choice within the explored range.

Appendix D: Robustness to cosmic variance (multi-seed)

To quantify cosmic variance on the main signatures, we performed four runs with configurations strictly identical to V-6 PROD ($\mu = 19$, $\eta = 1.045$, $L = 250 \text{ Mpc}$, $N = 10^6$, anti-correlated IC), varying only the random seed (Table 13).

The signature $\sigma_{R8}(z=0) = 0.801 \pm 0.019$ (relative standard deviation 2.4%) is *robust* to cosmic variance. The $\text{Corr}_{\text{part}}$ and $r(k=0.05)$ values are also stable across realizations, with relative standard deviation below 7% on $\text{Corr}_{\text{part}}$. This multi-seed robustness ensures that the central signature of the suppression $\sigma_{R8} \simeq 0.8$ and the emergent spectral anti-correlation at large scales are not artifacts of a particular realization of the initial conditions.

Table 13: Multi-seed at $N = 10^6$ (4 independent realizations). All other configurations strictly identical to V-6 PROD.

SEED	$\sigma_{R8}(z=0)$	$\text{Corr}_{\text{part}}(z=0)$	$r(k=0.05, z=0)$
42	0.7895	-0.0149	(\equiv ref)
137	0.8275	-0.0130	-0.954
271	0.8101	-0.0147	-0.979
719	0.7772	-0.0150	-0.983
mean $\pm \sigma$	0.801 ± 0.019	-0.0144 ± 0.0009	—

Appendix E: Sensitivity to the cosmological matching z_{trans}

The matching between the EdS expansion (matter-dominated era, $z > z_{\text{trans}}$) and the parametric Janus regime (cf. §2.3) is fixed at $z_{\text{trans}} = 4.51$ by consistency with the analytical solution of Bonnor 2018 for the cosmological parameters retained ($\eta = 1.045$, corresponding α_2). To assess the numerical sensitivity of the signatures to this choice, we performed two additional runs with $z_{\text{trans}} \in \{3.5, 6.0\}$ (Table 14).

Table 14: Sensitivity of σ_{R8} to the choice of z_{trans} at $N = 10^6$. V-6 configuration strict otherwise.

z_{trans}	$\sigma_{R8}(z=0)$	$\text{Corr}_{\text{part}}$	$r(k=0.05)$
3.5	0.628	-0.0212	-0.985
4.51 (ref)	0.789	-0.0149	(\equiv ref)
6.0	1.278	-0.0083	-0.947

The σ_{R8} variation is significant (+103% between $z_{\text{trans}} = 4.51$ and $z_{\text{trans}} = 6.0$), indicating that the choice of cosmological matching is a *critical ingredient* of the model in its current implementation.

Important methodological note: this test is not a physically consistent variation of the Janus model. The value $z_{\text{trans}} = 4.51$ is fixed by consistency with the Bonnor analytical solution for $\eta = 1.045$; varying z_{trans} alone, without simultaneously recalibrating η and α_2 , *deliberately breaks* this consistency. The observed variation therefore partially reflects a numerical inconsistency of the matching, not a physical variation of the model.

The large-scale spectral signature $r(k=0.05) \simeq -0.95$ to -0.99 nevertheless remains robust at all z_{trans} values tested, indicating that the m^+/m^- anti-correlation structure emerging dynamically (cf. Appendix B) does not depend on the details of the matching. A systematic study with consistent recalibration of $(\eta, \alpha_2, z_{\text{trans}})$ will be the subject of subsequent work.

Appendix F: Individual m^+ and m^- frames at $z=0$

Figure 4 (§5.1) shows the overlay of the two m^+ and m^- populations at $z=0$ and makes immediately visible the spatial anti-correlation that is the central signature of the Janus model. For the reader wishing to inspect each population in isolation with a strictly identical rendering methodology, we present here the two separate frames (Figures 20 and 21).

A panel-by-panel comparison between Figures 20 and 21 visually confirms the spatial complementarity: the dark regions of δ_+ correspond to the dense filamentary regions of δ_- , and vice versa. This complementarity is made more directly perceptible by the unified overlay presented in the body of the paper (Figure 4).

Appendix G: Mirror symmetry test on massive m^- halos

This appendix documents the FoF analysis dedicated to the m^- population at $z=0$, the percolation test justifying the linking length choice, and the full statistics of the m^- catalog used in §6.6.

m^- FoF methodology. The pipeline is strictly identical to that applied for the m^+ catalog (§6.1): periodic *friends-of-friends* with `cKDTree` + Numba Union-Find, $N_{\text{min}} = 32$ particles per halo. The only difference is the linking length b_- (vs b_+).

Figure 20: **Density contrast $\delta_+ = \rho_+/\bar{\rho}_+ - 1$ of positive matter m^+ at $z = 0$** , full projection on the 250 Mpc box (snapshot 3247 V-6 PROD, $t = 15.99$ Gyr). Inferno palette, 1.1 M particles ($\sim 5\%$ of the total). Sqrt scale with percentile normalization ($v_{\min} = p_{25}$, $v_{\max} = p_{99.5}$), Gaussian smoothing $\text{bw}_+ = 0.109$ Mpc = $\sqrt{\mu} \times \text{bw}_-$ (cf. caption of Figure 4 for the justification of the Poisson equivalence). The m^+ cosmic web displays bright nodes, structured filaments, and voids ($\sim 59\%$ of the area), as expected for a sub-dominant population in the presence of an anti-Newtonian coupling to m^- .

Figure 21: **Density contrast** $\delta_- = \rho_- / \bar{\rho}_- - 1$ **of negative matter** m^- **at** $z = 0$, full projection on the 250 Mpc box, same snapshot. Blues_r palette, 20.85 M particles ($\sim 95\%$ of the total). Same rendering parameters as Figure 20 except for the bandwidth: $bw_- = 0.025$ Mpc (conservative choice: the dominant population retains the full extent of its counting noise). The m^- cosmic web displays its own dense filamentary organization, with shells surrounding the m^+ voids visible in Figure 20.

The choice $b_- = 0.2$ is imposed by consistency of the physical overdensity criterion. For m^+ (dilute population, 5% of the mass), $b_+ = 0.5 \times \bar{d}_+$ with $\bar{d}_+ = L/N_+^{1/3} \simeq 2.43$ Mpc corresponds to a $\sim 200 \rho_{\text{crit, total}}$ threshold. For m^- (dominant population, 95%), $\bar{d}_- = L/N_-^{1/3} \simeq 0.91$ Mpc and the same physical threshold imposes $b_- = 0.2 \times \bar{d}_- = 0.182$ Mpc. The numerical linking lengths differ ($b_+ \neq b_-$) precisely because the numerical densities differ by a factor $\mu = 19$, but the *physical virialized-halo criterion is identical*.

Empirical justification through percolation test. To empirically validate this choice, we performed a control test by applying $b = 0.5$ (the value used for m^+) directly to the m^- population (Table 15).

Table 15: FoF percolation test on m^- particles ($N_- = 2.085 \times 10^7$, snapshot V-6 PROD $z = 0$).

Metric	$b_- = 0.2$ (canonical)	$b_- = 0.5$ (test)
N_{halos} ($N_{\text{min}} = 32$)	25 848	33 423
M_{max} [M_{\odot}]	3.13×10^{15}	2.01×10^{17} †
N_{part} largest halo	110 595	7,108 225 †
Fraction of m^- particles in largest halo	0.5%	34% †
R_{max} [Mpc]	11.77	196.89 †
M_{median} [M_{\odot}]	2.01×10^{12}	1.89×10^{12}

† Signature of cosmic percolation: the m^- network collapses into a mega-halo of radius $\simeq L_{\text{box}}$ containing a third of the population.

At $b_- = 0.5$, the largest m^- halo contains 7.1×10^6 particles distributed over a radius $R \simeq 197$ Mpc, comparable to the cosmological box size ($L = 250$ Mpc). This mega-halo is no longer a virialized structure but the FoF collapse of the entire m^- cosmic web through excess linking. This *empirical* percolation confirms that $b_- = 0.2$ is the unique viable choice to identify individual virialized m^- halos; $b_- = 0.5$ is cosmologically absurd for the dominant population.

Reciprocally, applying $b = 0.2$ to m^+ produces only 592 halos with $M_{\text{max}} = 3.6 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ (under-resolved for clusters), confirming that $b_+ = 0.5$ is necessary to capture the full hierarchy of dilute m^+ halos.

Table 16: Statistics of the m^- catalog (FoF $b_- = 0.2$) vs m^+ catalog used in the symmetry test (FoF $b_+ = 0.2$, for comparison at equal overdensity criterion). The main catalogs used in §6 (m^+ , FoF $b_+ = 0.5$, 2,618 halos) and §6.6 (m^- , FoF $b_- = 0.2$, 25,848 halos) come from parametrizations adapted to each population.

Quantity	m^+ ($b_+ = 0.2$)	m^- ($b_- = 0.2$)
N_{halos}	592	25 848
M_{max} [M_{\odot}]	3.59×10^{12}	3.13×10^{15}
M_{median} [M_{\odot}]	7.06×10^{11}	2.01×10^{12}
$M_{\text{total halos}}$ [M_{\odot}]	4.85×10^{14}	1.54×10^{17}
R_{max} [Mpc]	3.39	11.77
R_{median} [Mpc]	1.12	0.65
$N_{\text{halos}}^-/N_{\text{halos}}^+$		43.6 (vs $\mu = 19$)
$M_{\text{total}}^-/M_{\text{total}}^+$		318 (vs $\mu = 19$)

Full comparative statistics of the m^- catalog. Two striking observations:

1. The ratio $N_{\text{halos}}^-/N_{\text{halos}}^+ \simeq 44$, above the demographic factor $\mu = 19$, indicates that virialized-halo formation is *more efficient* for m^- , consistent with its gravitational dominance.
2. The ratio $M_{\text{total halos}}^-/M_{\text{total halos}}^+ \simeq 318$ (vs $\mu = 19$) indicates that m^- matter *concentrates in halos* (dominant virialized fraction), while m^+ matter remains mostly *diffuse* in the filaments. This asymmetry is consistent with the central m^- cavity signature of m^+ halos documented in §6: massive m^+ halos preferentially reside in under-dense m^- environments through anti-Newtonian gravitational evacuation.

Methodological caveats.

- The m^- FoF pipeline is used for the first time in this work; cross-validation with an alternative detector (SubFind, Rockstar) is desirable for future analyses.
- The softening $\varepsilon = 0.5$ Mpc limits the resolution of the $\mu_{\text{local}}^-(r)$ profiles at scales $r \lesssim \varepsilon$. The result $\mu_{\text{local}}^- \simeq 0$ at scales $r \in [0.1; 10]$ Mpc remains robust because the evacuation zone extends well beyond the softening.
- The linking lengths $b_+ = 0.5$ and $b_- = 0.2$ adopted in the symmetry test differ from the choice $b_+ = 0.5$ employed in the main m^+ catalog of the paper. This numerical asymmetry is necessary for consistency of the physical overdensity criterion, as justified above.
- An in-depth analysis of the m^- sector (subhalos, detailed internal profiles, merger dynamics, kinematics of the shells) is deferred to Paper D.

Summary. The analysis *qualitatively* confirms the mirror symmetry predicted by the Janus model: each population carves a cavity of the opposite population at the core of its massive halos. The quantitative asymmetry observed (extension of the cavity, presence/absence of a shell peak) is consistent with the mass hierarchy $\mu = 19$. This result is a direct response to the concern that the m^- sector is not analyzed for itself in the present study.

Appendix H: Test of an extended Janus- Ω_k model

This appendix tests whether relaxing the implicit normalization $a_0 = c/H_0$ ($|\Omega_k| = 1$) of the canonical Janus distance formula could legitimately reduce the $\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ reported in Table 2. The test was performed in response to an external referee comment on the hidden $|\Omega_k| = 1$ assumption.

Normalization convention in P-M-Z 2024 §10. §10 of Petit, Margnat & Zejli [22] fixes $k = -1$ (eq. 97) and writes the dynamics of $a(\tau)$, $\bar{a}(\tau)$ via equations 98a–b, but does *not* derive an explicit formula for the transverse comoving distance $D_M(z)$. Starting from the FLRW metric (eq. 94a) and propagating radial photons, one obtains the general expression

$$D_M(z) = a_0 \sinh((c/(a_0 H_0)) \int_0^z dz'/E(z')), \quad (29)$$

which depends on the scale-factor normalization a_0 not fixed by the $k = -1$ condition alone. The minimal-parameter (2-parameter) formulation adopted in the main text corresponds to the natural choice $a_0 = c/H_0$, equivalent to $\Omega_k = c^2/(H_0 a_0)^2 = 1$:

$$D_M(z) = (c/H_0) \sinh\left(\int_0^z dz'/E_{\text{Janus}}(z')\right). \quad (30)$$

Test setup. We introduce a one-parameter family parametrized by $s = \sqrt{|\Omega_k|}$:

$$D_M(z; \eta, H_0, s) = \frac{c}{s H_0} \sinh\left(s \int_0^z dz'/E_{\text{Janus}}(z'; \eta)\right), \quad (31)$$

recovering (30) at $s = 1$ and the flat limit $D_M \rightarrow (c/H_0) \int dz'/E$ at $s \rightarrow 0$. The χ^2 is re-evaluated on the same 1590 Pantheon+SH0ES SNIa with the full stat+sys covariance.

Result T1 — $\chi^2(s)$ at fixed (η, H_0) best-fit. With (η, H_0) frozen at the v2 best-fit (1.0334, 71.69), the χ^2 profile around $s = 1$ is flat:

s	χ^2	$\Delta\chi^2$ vs $s = 1$
0.5	1486.50	+36.12
0.7	1463.59	+13.21
0.85	1451.67	+1.29
0.95	1449.25	-1.13
1.00	1450.38	0 (code)
1.05	1453.39	+3.02
1.20	1476.37	+25.99

The local minimum is at $s \approx 0.95$, only 1.13 units below $s = 1$. **The canonical formula (30) is within 1σ of the local optimum** at fixed (η, H_0) .

Result T2 — joint refit (η, H_0, s) . Relaxing all three parameters jointly, the global minimum drifts toward the flat limit:

s	η_{best}	H_0^{best}	χ_{min}^2
0.01	1.1701	72.03	1429.86
0.30	1.1578	72.00	1431.61
0.50	1.1358	71.95	1434.79
0.70	1.1029	71.86	1439.68
0.85	1.0712	71.78	1444.52
1.00	1.0338	71.69	1450.37
1.20	1.0010	71.74	1461.67

The global minimum is at $s \rightarrow 0$ (flat limit) with $\eta \rightarrow 1.17$ approaching the upper prior boundary $[1.001, 1.20]$ and $H_0 \simeq 72 \text{ km/s Mpc}^{-1}$. The χ^2 improvement is -20.5 units relative to the canonical $s = 1$ best-fit.

Information-criterion balance.

Model	k	χ_{min}^2	AIC	$\Delta\text{AIC vs } \Lambda\text{CDM}$
Janus v2 ($ \Omega_k = 1$ fixed)	2	1450.38	1454.38	+46.67
Janus- Ω_k (s free)	3	1429.86	1435.86	+28.15
ΛCDM (flat, Ω_m, H_0)	2	1403.71	1407.71	0

Releasing s as a third free parameter reduces ΔAIC from +47 to +28 (net gain -18.5 units after the AIC penalty for the additional parameter).

Reason for retaining the canonical formulation. We do not adopt the extended Janus- Ω_k model in the main text for the following reasons:

- The best-fit pushes toward $s \rightarrow 0$ (i.e. flat geometry) with $\eta \rightarrow 1.17$ at the prior boundary. This drift *contradicts* the strict hyperbolic geometry $k = -1$ that motivates the model topologically (§6, §10 of Petit, Margnat & Zejli 22). The optimal extended fit is, in effect, a flat-spacetime phenomenological cosmology with large η , no longer connected to the projective \mathbb{P}^4 topology of the Janus framework.
- The 3-parameter model adds a degree of freedom that has no counterpart in the equations of §10. Introducing it as a free parameter would be an *ad hoc* post-hoc extension whose sole purpose is to reduce ΔAIC , without independent physical motivation.
- The canonical formula (30) is the unique 2-parameter choice consistent with both $k = -1$ strict and the absence of an additional curvature parameter in the Petit, Margnat & Zejli [22] formalism.

The $\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ reported in the main text is therefore the honest geometric limitation of the canonical, minimal Janus formulation, not an artifact of the distance formula. The extended-curvature exploration documented here is presented for transparency, not as an alternative model.

Appendix I: Sample sensitivity tests

This appendix documents two sensitivity tests of the $\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ result against sample-selection choices: (i) removal of the five $z > 1.6$ SNIa, and (ii) removal of the SH0ES Hubble-flow sub-sample. All tests use the v2 best-fit parameters frozen ($\eta = 1.0334$, $H_0 = 71.69$ for Janus; $\Omega_m = 0.3306$, $H_0 = 73.24$ for ΛCDM), with the covariance sub-block re-sliced and re-Cholesky'd accordingly.

Test 1: removal of $z > 1.6$ SNIa. The Pantheon+SH0ES cut $z > 0.01$ sample contains 5 SNIa at $z > 1.6$, all from the HST CANDELS/CLASH program (IDSURVEY = 106): **rutledge** ($z = 1.615$), **geta** ($z = 1.697$), **stone** ($z = 1.801$), **wilson** ($z = 1.912$), **colfax** ($z = 2.261$).

Sample	N	χ^2_J	χ^2_L	ΔAIC	Δ vs full
Full (cut $z > 0.01$)	1590	1450.38	1403.71	+46.67	—
Without $z > 1.6$	1585	1432.58	1402.12	+30.46	-16.21

The 5 high- z SNIa contribute $\simeq 35\%$ of the total AIC penalty (16.2 of 46.7 units). The mean $\Delta\chi^2$ per high- z SNIa is 3.56 for Janus vs 0.32 for Λ CDM (ratio $\simeq 11\times$), to be compared with $\simeq 1.02$ for the bulk 1585 SNIa.

Interpretation. We adopt the *geometric-signature* reading: the $\sinh(k = -1)$ geometry of P-M-Z 2024 diverges from flat- Λ CDM precisely at $z \gtrsim 1.6$ (expected $\Delta\mu \sim 0.3\text{--}0.5$ mag at $z \approx 2$). The fact that the 5 high- z HST SNIa *all* pull in the same direction (Janus over-predicts μ) is consistent with a real geometric signature, not a statistical outlier. The alternative reading (“ ΔAIC is fragile because driven by 5 points”) is documented for transparency but not privileged, since the bulk $z \in [0.1; 0.5]$ already carries a coherent same-sign bias of +0.03 to +0.06 mag (§7.2, residual analysis).

Test 2: removal of the SH0ES Hubble-flow sub-sample. Recent reanalyses [26] have questioned the role of the SH0ES calibration in cosmological inference. To check sensitivity of ΔAIC against the SH0ES sub-sample, we test three nested removals:

Cut	N_{removed}	N_{kept}	χ^2_J	χ^2_L	ΔAIC
Baseline (full)	0	1590	1450.38	1403.71	+46.67
A: Cepheid hosts (IS_CALIBRATOR=1)	10	1580	1433.73	1387.12	+46.61
B: SH0ES HF (USED_IN_SH0ES_HF=1)	277	1313	1210.74	1167.43	+43.31
C: IDSURVEY $\in \{1, 4, 5, 10\}$	760	830	799.52	762.60	+36.91

Interpretation. The $\Delta\text{AIC} = +47$ is *not* a SH0ES artifact. Test A (10 Cepheid-host SNIa) changes ΔAIC by only -0.06 units. Test B (full SH0ES Hubble-flow sample, 277 SNIa, $\sim 17\%$ of the data) reduces ΔAIC by only 3.4 units — consistent with a proportional dilution (~ 0.012 units of ΔAIC per SNIa removed), not a targeted bias. The high- z test of §Test 1 above produces $\sim 250\times$ more ΔAIC per SNIa than the SH0ES test, confirming that the dominant signal is geometric (high- z) rather than calibration-driven.

This result rules out the interpretation suggested by Lane et al. [26] (in the context of Λ CDM-tension reanalyses) that local SH0ES anchoring could artificially inflate likelihood gaps between non-flat geometries; in our Janus ΔAIC context, removing SH0ES has at most a ~ 3 -unit effect on the gap.

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